

MAMMAL RESEARCH INSTITUTE 50th ANNIVERSARY SYMPOSIUM

SYNOPSSES & ABSTRACTS

(in order of appearance in the programme)

Opening address

50 years of MRI mammal research

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SUMMARY

Since its genesis 50 years ago the Mammal Research Institute at the University of Pretoria has been a leader in the field of behaviour, ecology, physiology and taxonomy of both terrestrial and aquatic mammals. The Institute has been led by five directors, namely Jurgens Meester, John Skinner, Johan du Toit, Elissa Cameron and Robert Millar who have pushed and promoted mammalogy and made the MRI globally recognised. In this talk the history of the contributions of its Directors, staff, students and collaborators are reviewed as well as the highlights and achievements. At the end of the talk some future directions are proposed to further promote the institute as a national Centre of Excellence.

Theme 1: People and Wildlife

Integrative Mammalogy

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SYNOPSIS

The science of Mammalogy has evolved rapidly over the last few decades. There have been two important drivers of the evolution of the discipline. First, the harnessing of numerous opportunities presented by emergent technologies such as telemetry, radio-isotopes studies, genome sequencing and digital photography. Secondly, Mammalogy has fragmented into specialised sub-disciplinary areas, each with their own journals such as molecular, whole organisms and ecosystem studies, with limited conceptual integration across these boundaries.

What does this mean for the future of Mammalogy? Clearly, mammal species around the globe are under severe threat, this despite considerable attempts to step up our conservation efforts, to emphasise their potential and real eco-tourism benefits, sustainable use options as well as the introduction of many innovative community-based wildlife conservation programmes. The intensification of broad-based mammal distribution mapping, taxonomic and population delineation and related population dynamic studies as a basis for improving our understanding of the real conservation pressures are important and should continue at an accelerated pace. Here mammalogists can and should continue to play an important contributing role. However, whether this can be the *raison d'être* for the continued strength and impact of the discipline is not clear. There are far more powerful and better positioned forces and organisations in the conservation landscape that could play a leading role towards these broad scale mammal conservation ends, naturally leaning on the fundamental work done at institutions like the Mammal Research Institute.

However, the discipline and science of Mammalogy requires something more fundamental. There are two reasons for this. Most important is the recent resurgence of a more comprehensive understanding of zoological phenomena, on all levels of analysis, towards an integrative discipline, that stretches from the level of the gene to the ecosystem. The second is linked to modern trends in science funding. As science funding grows globally, the return on investment expectations are also affected - increasingly, funders and government investors are looking for big and meaningful impacts for their investments, this either means socio-economic returns or fundamental scientific contributions. In pursuit of the latter, science funding typically follows the U-shaped funding regime. In order to attract significant funding, you either have to be studying phenomena at an atomic or cosmic level (e.g. build colliders and/or expensive telescopes). For the life-sciences to attract significant funding, it is either about the big idea or issue (human genome project and HIV-Aids research) or building integrative platforms that will bring together large multidisciplinary research teams and collectively address key societal needs or research themes (NEON, SAEON in South Africa). The science of single entrepreneurial scientists working and being funded in isolation is not the dominant trend at the moment.

Consequently, for the discipline to flourish and continue to be most influential, it requires a core conceptual agenda that will be instantly recognised globally and nationally. I propose one such an idea, the establishment of an African "Mammatron". The most intensively studied and documented African large mammal system in the world. A site where the entire system is studied from the genome to the ecosystem level, where the most innovative technologies are deployed for this purpose (e.g. Sutherland review), where ecotourism and citizen science opportunities are harnessed and where disparate disciplinary specialists contribute in a transdisciplinary fashion to the development of Integrative Mammalogy. An intensively studied "Mammatron" will open up opportunities for the development of big data science, the fourth paradigm or data intensive science. This includes approaches such as multiscale modelling and systems approaches or biocomplexity research to take us beyond "flat earth" systems biology understanding. The philosophy behind this approach is akin to the Nylsvlei Savanna Ecosystem work conducted from the 1970's and what is now being attempted under the SAEON banner.

Such a unique "Mammatron" platform, that bring together many scientists and develops unique capabilities, has the potential to attract dedicated funding (nationally and internationally) and improve our fundamental understanding of mammal dominated ecosystems on the African continent. Key questions such as system tolerances and limits, system integrity requirements as well as key system disruptors and potential mitigation responses can be explored in a focused manner in a mammal dominated system of global significance.

A sub-Saharan perspective on conservation challenges for African mammals over the next two decades

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SYNOPSIS

There are enough firm pointers around that allow us to paint the picture of Africa in 2050 with a relatively degree of certainty. The continent will have twice its current population size, more than two thirds of whom will live in urban settlements. A burgeoning middle class in Africa will grow by fourfold over the same period, and through raised consumption patterns will substantially multiply their ecological footprint. Importantly, there will be a sustained rise in investment by those keen to be a part of Africa's growth story and there will be continued and growing global demand for primary agricultural and mineral resources. Together, these forces will have significant additional implications for food and water security, energy provision and the infrastructure necessary to support these growing needs and expectations.

This implies that Africa's ecological future will largely be dependent on (i) economic activities such as agriculture, extractive and manufacturing industries; (ii) urbanisation, through the degree to which human settlements are concentrated and the consequent goods and services that they consume; and (iii) the nature and extent of infrastructure that supports production and consumption (e.g. dams, roads, pipelines, ports and energy supplies), and conservation (i.e. ecological infrastructure such as aquatic ecosystems).

Given the significant pressures that Africa's ecological systems will be under over the next decades, a sustainable approach to conservation issues cannot be guided by a narrow paradigm that invariably separates the realms of biodiversity conservation from human wellbeing. In addition, in the broader landscape human wellbeing is fundamentally dependent on the integrity and healthy functioning of ecological systems. Thus, protected areas cannot be everything to everyone, while the ecosystems outside them will be compelled to work very hard without losing their integrity and function.

These pressure will compel mammal conservationists to significantly broaden their horizons. Of the 1100 known mammal species that occur in Africa, only a relatively small proportion are significantly dependent on the existence and proper functioning of protected areas. On the one hand, the integrity and long-term sustainability of protected areas will become increasingly vital. This requires at least four fundamental attributes, viz. strong governance systems, harmonious neighbour relations, sound ecological management, and high(ly) value(d) use of resources (consumptive and non-consumptive). On the other hand, careful spatial planning will be vital in order to ensure that the pressures driving habitat transformation avoid impacting areas of greatest environmental sensitivity and value.

Adaptive management of large wild mammals and livestock in Anthropocene ecosystems

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SYNOPSIS

Looking from the present into the past, across continents the onset and progression of the Anthropocene epoch coincided with shrinking populations and habitats of large wild mammals. Economically, wildlife conservation incurs opportunity costs so that wildlife can only outcompete livestock in arid and semi-arid regions. Ecologically, human-facilitated livestock populations dominate rangelands because of artificial water-provision and predator-control. Development of mixed (multi-species) systems is obstructed by the problem of disease transmission so that livestock and wildlife populations are seldom allowed to come together. But looking from the present into our Anthropocene future it is apparent that climate change and other anthropogenic stressors are pushing ecosystems beyond their resilience thresholds. Novel ecosystems are emerging that cannot be 'restored' to any historical benchmark.

Managers of such ecosystems have to operate within an adaptive framework in which experimentation and learning are essential, with a key challenge being the need to understand how to sustainably utilize the potential suite of ecosystem services. This requires reference to a functional typology of ecosystems classified in terms of bottom-up (soils and climate) and top-down (herbivores and fire) determinants. Now, a few large protected areas in Africa are the last refugia of functionally intact assemblages of large mammals, meaning all body-size classes and feeding styles of herbivores are still represented, together with the predators and scavengers that depend on them. These large mammal communities and their ecosystems - if effectively conserved - will become increasingly valuable as reference resources to guide the adaptive management of novel ecosystems on all continents. Hence, an important emphasis for research on large mammals in Africa is a mechanistic understanding of how functional types influence ecosystem processes. In novel ecosystems there are no indigenous, exotic, or feral species and so - if the challenges of disease transmission can be overcome - African large mammal assemblages could become templates for building their functional equivalents in novel ecosystems on other continents.

Current and future human population pressures on mammals in southern Africa

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SYNOPSIS

Ongoing extinctions, rising threat risk, and declining abundance of mammals over the last half century have occurred in concert with massive human modification of the biosphere. Arguably one of the most important drivers of biodiversity loss is habitat modification, and mainly in the form of forest and grassland conversion to agriculture, even though direct overexploitation in many species can be as or more important. As the only continent to escape the major extinction event of the late Pleistocene and early Holocene, Africa is in a unique position to maintain its mammal megafauna despite the rising pressures of human endeavour. However, direct and indirect threats are likely to increase as the human population in Africa expands, and as overseas demand for her timber, mining, agriculture and seafood resources continues to increase. In fact, southern Africa's current human population of just under 500 million is projected to increase by more than five-fold to nearly 3 billion people by 2100, one of the world's fastest-growing regions. Africa's slow rate of fertility decline (about 1/3 that of Asia and Latin America) and even stalling in some countries means that continent-wide, Africa's current total population of 1 billion is set to rise to 3.1-5.7 billion (95% confidence bounds) by the end of the century.

This inexorable expansion of the human population will undoubtedly exacerbate the extinction risk of many African mammal species, although the direct evidence for the negative effects of human population on biodiversity is often confounded with other conditions. For example, there is only a weak correlation globally between human population density and species extinctions because of spatial congruence between human population size and species richness, a lack of data on extinctions, and the variability across methods. However, there is evidence that current human population densities and growth rates are higher in Biodiversity Hotspots than elsewhere, and that there is a historical relationship between human population size and threats to biodiversity at national scales. In Europe, there is a century-scale time lag between increasing human population density and current biodiversity threat. Globally, human population density predicts the number of threatened species among nations and 50% of tropical protected areas are experiencing biodiversity loss because of high human population growth and locally or foreign-driven consumption at their edges. For these same protected areas, human population size is negatively correlated with a protected area's health.

I therefore hypothesised that human population density would explain variation in mammal diversity (data from biodiversitymapping.org) within southern Africa after accounting for other ecological and human-pressure variables. I sourced data on human population density from the Global Rural-Urban Mapping Project, road densities (as a proxy for urbanisation and habitat fragmentation) from the Global Roads Open Access Data Set, cropland intensity (from Navin Ramankutty, University of British Columbia) and habitat 'wetness' (as a proxy for productivity) from the Global Mean Aridity Index. Downscaling the datasets and randomly sub-sampling to avoid extensive spatial autocorrelation, I tested for multivariate correlations between the four predictors and mammal diversity using generalised linear models. Wetness was positively correlated with mammal diversity, and there was a negative effect of human population density. Changing the response variable to the diversity of threatened (IUCN Red List status VU to CR) mammals and offsetting the models for total mammal diversity, both generalised linear models and boosted regression trees indicated a non-linear increase in threatened mammal diversity with rising wetness, and a nonlinear decline with increasing human population and road densities (cropland intensity had little to no explanatory power in any of the models I constructed). Finally, combining the human pressure variables into the 2016 'Human Footprint' score provided little explanatory power.

Of course, human population is only one side of the pressure coin, with consumption itself interacting inseparably from the former. I therefore examined trends in CO₂-e emissions from 13 countries in southern Africa as a proxy for domestic consumption, and recent (2000-2014) deforestation as a proxy of combined domestic and overseas consumption. While the region's average per capita emissions have been approximately invariant at around 2 t CO₂-e from 1960 to today, the region's overall annual emissions have been increasing due to rising human populations from ~ 600-900 Mt CO₂-e over the same period, with most (> 95%) emissions originating from South Africa. Recent deforestation ranging from 0-2.5% of total country area over the last few decades is symptomatic of an increasing problem of both legal and illegal deforestation throughout the region (nearly 200000 km² net loss from 2000-2014 across the continent).

Future analyses should attempt to access data on relative mammal densities in the region to examine their relationships with human population densities, and to project areas of increasing urbanisation and wildlife conflict as the region's human population expands.

Getting the balance right for mammal research and conservation

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SYNOPSIS

There are great challenges ahead for mammal research and conservation, providing opportunities for new avenues of research to meet these challenges, but increasingly requiring balance between different goals. I discuss some of these balances that present additional challenges to conservation and need to be considered in planning research.

* Balancing the requirements of individual-focussed research and conservation with the conservation goals of conserving functioning populations and communities. As populations become more threatened and conservation actions require more intensive interventions such as captive breeding, reintroduction, translocation and management on small reserves, the focus of research shifts needs to shift more towards individuals than populations. New research has highlighted the importance of traits associated with individuals, such as social relationships, for the success of conservation outcomes. For example, intensive management results in altered physiological stress, which has implications for the survival and reproductive success of individuals, and the success of conservation interventions, but these effects are often hidden. Stress experienced during gestational development results in life-long changes in metabolism, stress reactivity and reproductive output. I discuss the implications of such non-genetic inheritance for conservation through the effects on individuals, with unexpected impacts on population dynamics.

* Balancing the requirements for strong disciplinary research with the requirement for increasingly transdisciplinary research and community consultation. Research excellence requires innovation and creativity, which increasingly derives from bringing together a diversity of disciplines and approaches - such as for this meeting. Such a diversity in scientific backgrounds and experiences leads to novel solutions to seemingly intractable problems not only in research but for conservation and sustainable development, core goals of the MRI. The key to success in conservation, however, is increasingly reliant on engagement with communities, since the conservation requires understanding the complex social-ecological systems, not just the ecosystems. Conservation decisions are not just biological, so require not only collaborative research across scientific disciplines, but increasingly involving social scientists and local communities. I discuss examples where these goals have been balanced for greater success in conservation outcomes.

* Balancing research excellence with a more inclusive research environment. Diversity is not limited to our professional backgrounds but also our life experiences, since our 'way of knowing' influences our approach to research. However, several societal groups continue to be under-represented in science. I outline some of the contributing factors to this attrition of under-represented groups, some of which will not easily change. I discuss ways in which such attrition could be addressed by ensuring our scientific systems are a real meritocracy, reflecting diverse views rather than traditional career paths.

In summary, as we face growing challenges, we need diversity in approaches to enhance creativity and innovation, which will be essential for future research and conservation breakthroughs. Balancing diverse views and approaches is essential to our future success in mammal research and conservation.

Combatting poaching in the Kruger National Park

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SYNOPSIS

Poaching has become immune to tradition counter poaching strategies. These strategies vary between paramilitary on one sphere of the pendulum to community participatory natural resource management on the other. In practice, these strategies are viewed as two separate approaches that are hardly complementing each other. There is no other place to demonstrate this silo approaches that within South African National Park (SANParks) using Kruger National Park (KNP) as a case study.

Historically protected areas were establishment to address the dwindling numbers of wildlife and to maintain habitat quality and quantity. To achieve these two objectives, human activities were limited in the areas. Societal understanding of ecological phenomena recognised the limitations and strengths of protected areas. These newly acquired expertise broaden the scope of protected areas to incorporate non-biological actors. The effects of protected areas' boundaries started to get attention from society and ecological scientists. Protected area agencies started looking beyond the boundaries. Different protected area agencies started adopting this beyond the boundary paradigm. Theoretical this new paradigm is compatible with the ecosystems approach to conservation of biodiversity at broad scale.

In recent years poaching has change its meaning more especial in South Africa where rhino poaching is strife. Traditionally; poaching was just for subsistence, but in the 21st security poaching has been commercialised. There are still some subsistence poaching that is happening at micro scale, but recently commercial poaching has overshadowed subsistence poaching. The main drivers of these wildlife crimes are man, money and machines or tools.

Poaching in Kruger National Parks have increased from 2007. This was becoming too much for the Rangers. The Minister of Environmental Affairs approached the security cluster, then South African Police (SAPS) and South African National Defence Force (SANDF) were brought to the mission area. From 2007 to 2014, there were steep increase in rhino poaching. In 2015; we have witnessed a stabilisation in rhino carcasses. There is a high increase on poacher activities. The arrest and firearms has increased. Elephant poaching is starting.

Rhino poaching has improved communication between protected area agencies that still have rhinos. In Mozambique both state and private concessions are showing signs of commitment and the incursions are decreasing from that side.

Natural Capital Accounting and Governance within expanding Oceans Economies

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ABSTRACT

Globally nations are expanding their economic footprint (as "ocean" or "blue" economies) into the ocean space (Operation Phakisa's unlocking of the South African ocean economy is one such example) with both an increase in the extent of existing industry sectors and the development and extension of emergent market sectors being proposed. Ocean ecosystem benefits to human welfare (as provisioning, regulatory or cultural ecosystem services) extend well beyond national economies in terms of GDP, yet the erosion of natural capital is seldom accounted for within national economic accounting systems such as the System of National Accounts (SNA). Governance of both inter-sectoral and sectoral-environmental conflicts are required in resource-use expansion within the limited ocean space, with governance viewed as informed decision making allowing trade-offs between conflicting resource-user needs and environmental sustainability requirements. Whilst Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) is oftproposed as a panacea for governance of such conflicts, it remains problematic. Ecosystem accounting is a novel and emergent field which integrates ecological and bio-physical information in a spatial framework to identify and monitor changes in the natural capital of ecosystems and the relationship of identified changes to economic and human activity as specified in the System of Environmental Accounting - Experimental Ecosystem Accounting (SEA EEA) framework. In doing so ecosystem accounting evaluates the condition and extent of spatial ecosystem assets and the flows of services (as support services between or within ecosystems, or as final ecosystem services to economic and other human activity). While South Africa has been identified to pilot SEA EEA ecosystem accounting, the framework has yet to be applied to the marine sector. This talk introduces natural capital and ecosystem accounting within the context of an expanding South African oceans economy.

Feast now, pay later: The Cost of Foraging at Wastewater Works for an Urban Adapter, the Banana Bat (*Neoromicia nana*)

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ABSTRACT

Wastewater Treatment Works (WWTWs) are a ubiquitous feature of the urban landscape. WWTWs may provide profitable foraging areas for insectivorous bats because of particularly high abundances of pollution-tolerant chironomid midges [1]. However, bats that feed on these insects may also accumulate pollutants in their tissues [2]. There have been no studies to investigate whether African bats utilize WWTWs as foraging grounds, and the potential physiological impacts from foraging at such sites. The aim of this study was to investigate the impact of WWTWs on foraging ecology and multiple tiers of physiology (haematology and genotoxicity, detoxification organs and reproduction) in an urban adapter, the banana bat (*Neoromicia nana*) in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. *N. nana* at wastewater-polluted sites exhibited significantly higher abundance and feeding activity, and a predominantly Dipteran diet compared to a diverse insect diet at unpolluted sites. WWTWs thus provide an abundant short-term food resource for bats. However, we found significantly higher metal levels at wastewater-polluted sites, and in tissues of these bats compared to unpolluted sites. Further, we found significant sub-lethal haematological and genotoxic responses (decreased antioxidant capacity, increased DNA damage and haematocrits) in WWTW bats. Thus, longer-term effects should be most evident in organs involved in detoxification. Indeed, we found disrupted essential metal/ mineral nutrient balance, histopathological tissue damage and whole organ effects in the liver/kidneys. Finally, we found reproductive system alterations in male *N. nana* at WWTWs. Although we did not find significant effects on sex organs, testosterone hormone concentrations were significantly lower in males at WWTWs than at unpolluted sites. In addition, their body condition indices were significantly lower than at unpolluted sites, suggesting lower quality male bats at WWTWs. Taken together, these results suggest potentially serious long-term health risks, negative fitness implications and ultimately, population effects for these top predators within the urban landscape.

[1] I. M. Abbot, D. P. Sleeman, and S. Harrison, "Bat Activity Affected By Sewage Effluent In Irish Rivers", *Biological Conservation*, 142, 2904 - 2914 (2009).

[2] K. J. Park, and A. Cristinacce, "Use Of Sewage Treatment Works As Foraging Sites By Insectivorous Bats" *Animal Conservation*, 9, 259 - 268 (2006).

A historical perspective on the use and demand for rhinoceros products

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ABSTRACT

The unsustainable harvesting of rhinoceros, throughout history, has decimated their populations globally. Conservationists are in a constant, and often losing battle, to protect rhinoceros from poachers. However, the problem is not simply that people are poaching rhinoceros but that people desire rhinoceros horn. The question is why?

Using complex adaptive systems and path dependent analysis frameworks, the changing use and value of rhinoceros products in Greco-Roman, European, Middle Eastern, East Asian, Indian, and African cultures were analysed, thus illustrating what may have initiated, maintained, increased, and reduced demand. This analysis has demonstrated that the trade system is dynamic and has been influenced by availability, economic, cultural, and social factors, in multiple cultures and over thousands of years.

We show that the demand for, and associated use of, rhinoceros horn is a highly adaptive and unpredictable system, which cannot be effectively managed through symptomatic attack on poaching. Although, anti-poaching may be necessary for their immediate protection, a deeper understanding of the demand and trade system is required in order to produce strategies that will be effective in reducing poaching and ensuring the survival of the rhinoceros. This historical perspective provides an appreciation of socio-economic players and insight into potential holistic approaches to rhinoceros conservation.

Large mammals matter: ecological feedbacks from distorted African herbivore communities

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ABSTRACT

Native large mammal herbivore populations have been severely depleted across the globe, with profound consequences for ecological dynamics. Rewilding initiatives and inadvertent pathways like livestock farming have re-established large mammal herbivores in many regions, however, distortion of the historical biomass and functional type composition of herbivore communities may have radically altered ecosystem processes. We explore how African herbivore communities have been transformed over the last ~1000 years, by contrasting livestock-dominated current day herbivore communities with reconstructed historical herbivore communities. This reveals pronounced biomass losses in wetter areas and marked functional type turnover in arid regions. The ecological consequences of these shifts in the form and intensity of herbivory include alterations to biogeochemical cycling, fire prevalence and woody plant dynamics across the continent. Methane emissions and

nutrient diffusion capacity are likely lower than historical levels, most notably in mesic systems. Increased grazer biomass appears to have reduced fire prevalence over much of the continent, which coupled with the net effect of shifts in herbivore community composition, is likely to have released demographic bottlenecks for woody vegetation. Quantifying the changes that have occurred in African herbivore communities provides significant context for understanding a range of important ecosystem processes. Furthermore, it emphasises the necessity of incorporating feedbacks from large mammal herbivores into projections of the ecological trajectory of African ecosystems.

Reconciling wildlife conservation and land reform

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ABSTRACT

The need to address historical imbalances in land tenure is a common theme in African politics. Protecting biodiversity and maintaining the contribution of wildlife to the economy, to ecosystems and cultures is not always top priority when implementing land reform initiatives. We explore the impact of land reform on the status of medium and large mammals in Savé Valley Conservancy, Zimbabwe, as a case study, and provide recommendations on how land reform could be better managed. We used spoor counts to estimate the spoor density of mammals on land that had not been resettled, land that had been resettled, and communal land, as an index of relative abundance across these land use types. Furthermore, we estimated the absolute density and abundance of cheetah (*Acinonyx jubatus*), leopard (*Panthera pardus*), lion (*Panthera leo*), African wild dog (*Lycaon pictus*), spotted hyaena (*Crocuta crocuta*) and brown hyaena (*Parahyaena brunnea*). We found the greatest biodiversity levels and relative population densities of almost all mammals on private land, where population densities of large carnivores were comparable to protected areas [1]. Land that had been resettled supported much lower levels of biodiversity and lower relative population densities, although these were not quite as low as on communal land [2]. The decline in tourism and the economy has also been linked to the way land reform was executed [3, 4]. We recommend retaining wildlife-related land uses when implementing land reform programmes, preserving existing capital and expertise, and developing novel approaches, to ameliorate these problems for both wildlife and society.

[1] S. T. Williams, K. S. Williams, C. J. Joubert, and R. A. Hill, "The impact of land reform on the status of large carnivores in Zimbabwe". PeerJ, 4, e1537 (2016).

[2] S. T. Williams, "The impact of land reform in Zimbabwe on the conservation of cheetahs and other large carnivores". PhD thesis, Durham University, (2011).

[3] C. J. Richardson, "How much did droughts matter? Linking rainfall and GDP growth in Zimbabwe". African Affairs, 106, 463-478 (2007).

[4] H. Manwa, "Wildlife-based tourism, ecology and sustainability: a tug-of-war among competing interests in Zimbabwe". Journal of Tourism Studies, 14, 45-54 (2003).

Scales of injustice: Pangolins in the African bushmeat commodity chain

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ABSTRACT

All eight species of pangolins, in the unique order of Pholidota, are threatened with extinction primarily as a result of the large illicit trade within and into Asia where these mammals are highly prized as a delicacy and also extensively used as a source of traditional medicine. While limited records exist documenting the level and extent of the trade of pangolins from Africa to Asia, very little information is available where studies have investigated the local trade and harvest of the four African pangolins for bushmeat and traditional medicine. This study investigated 153 bush meat traders and interviewed 48 traditional healers in Ghana, 63 traditional healers in Sierra Leone and 344 traditional healers in South Africa as to the need, harvest and use of Temminck's Ground Pangolin (*Smutsia temminckii*) in South Africa and the Black-bellied Pangolin (*Phataginus tetradactyla*) and White-bellied Pangolin (*Phataginus tricuspis*) in Ghana and Sierra Leone. A total of 341 pangolins were observed to be traded as a source of bush meat in Ghana over a five month period, the majority (82%) being *P. tricuspis*. The use of various pangolin body parts are sought for traditional medicine; 13 in Ghana, 22 in Sierra Leone and 16 in South Africa to treat a multitude of physical and spiritual ailments. In all three countries the scales of the animal followed by its bones are most sought after. This study highlights the high demand for pangolin bush meat in Ghana and its high importance value associated with these mammals in Ghana, Sierra Leone and South Africa as part of these communities' spiritual, cultural and medical beliefs. However, the numbers of individual pangolins harvested for local trade from the wild remains unknown but is likely highly unsustainable and detrimental to African pangolin populations.

Figure 1 (a)

Figure 1 (b)

Fig. 1. (a) Black-bellied Pangolin (*Phataginus tetradactyla*) and (b) White-bellied Pangolin (*Phataginus tricuspis*) are traded regularly in west African bush-meat markets

The MRI's role in whale and dolphin research in southern Africa: Leading or lagging?

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ABSTRACT

For many years, the MRI has been a leader in the field of cetacean research in southern Africa, culminating in the seminal book, "Whales and Dolphins of the Southern African Subregion", by the late Prof Peter Best, development of a biennial conference series (The African Marine Mammal Colloquium, 2010-2016), a special issue of the African Journal of Marine Science and a review paper of published research in the southern African Subregion from the 1800s until 2010 (Elwen et al. 2010). MRI staff, students or graduates played a significant role in these outputs, with every paper in the special issue including at least one of the above. Over 550 peer-reviewed papers and books were included in the 2010 review paper. More than half (284) were produced since 1990 and 193 relate specifically to South African waters. The most-studied species up until that point are those species that are most accessible due to their coastal distributions (southern right whale *Eubalaena australis*: 45 papers, humpback whale *Megaptera novaengliae*: 31 papers, killer whales *Orcinus orca*: 27 papers, Indo-Pacific bottlenose dolphin *Tursiops aduncus*: 30 papers, Indo-Pacific humpback dolphin *Sousa chinensis (plumbea form)*: 25 papers) and/or were hunted commercially (sperm whale *Physeter macrocephalus*: 25 papers). In this talk, I will update the Elwen et al 2010 review paper, assess recent changes in research goals and tools, the response of the scientific community to the knowledge gaps detailed therein and evaluate the MRI's role in this growing field.

Framing human-wildlife conflict management: a typology

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ABSTRACT

Human wildlife conflict is frequently portrayed as a 'problem' that has to be 'controlled' instead of as a challenge of coexistence. There is currently no classification system or typology to distinguish between the divergent framings of the management of human wildlife conflict. Frames help humans to make sense of the world and mostly exist in people's minds, influencing their actions by stealth [1]. The framing of human-wildlife conflict management has important implications for the way strategies and interventions are conceived and implemented. Making such frames explicit could raise wildlife managers' awareness of their own frames and how this might affect their strategies and actions. This could challenge conventional views and open up new possibilities in research, development and implementation. We studied a broad range of articles on conflict management between humans and elephants, primates and large felids, published between 1996 and 2016 and discovered management interventions could be located along two gradients. The first, from biocentric to anthropocentric, signaled whether the target of the intervention was humans or wildlife. The second, between simplistic and complex, indicated whether the problem was perceived as uni-dimensional and 'tame', or alternatively complex and 'wicked'. When graphically represented along two axes (Figure 1), these gradients yielded four main framings: AC: Anthropocentric Controlling; BC: Biocentric Controlling; AA: Anthropocentric Adaptive; BA: Biocentric Adaptive. Positive consequences, and the fewest number of unintended consequences, were associated with interventions in the 'adaptive' (top) quadrants. Interventions that combined several foci from biocentric to anthropocentric were more likely to have positive consequences for humans and wildlife. To avoid unintended negative consequences, managers should strive to frame or re-frame human-wildlife conflict management as adaptive and co-existing, using a combination of anthropo- and biocentric foci. This is consistent with the social-ecological systems approach to conservation management [2].

Figure 1. Proposed typology for human-wildlife conflict management. Explanations are in the text

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Love and hate between family members: flexible primate neophilia in anthropogenically modified landscapes

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ABSTRACT

The risk-disturbance hypothesis is bolstered by many studies indicating that wild animals react to humans and their infrastructure as they would to natural predators. However, the relationship between human and non-human animals is complex and it remains challenging to predict which species will thrive or fail in human-modified landscapes. One prediction that has emerged from the field of urban ecology is that successful urban species are those who are more attracted to novel objects (i.e., neophilic species) and exhibit more innovative behaviour. It remains unclear whether these generalisations can apply to species or populations as a whole, or to what extent individual animals may modify their risk-taking behaviour when interacting with humans and their infrastructure. We investigated both risk-taking behaviour and neophilia in a population of samango monkeys, *Cercopithecus mitis erytharcus*, whose home range overlaps both disturbed and undisturbed habitats. Using a Giving-Up Densities approach and the presentation of a series of novel objects, we assessed whether or not these monkeys alter their risk-taking behavior in the gardens, compared to the natural forests of Hogsback, Eastern Cape, South Africa. Our results suggest that these monkeys exhibit flexible risk-taking behavior in response to human habitat alteration, suggesting that wild animals optimize their responses to humans, a species that represents both opportunity and risk to most wildlife. We discuss a number of approaches to the assessment of animals' landscape of fear, particularly as it pertains to human-wildlife conflict.

Fig. 1. A samango monkey digging through inedible matrix to obtain food items in a Giving-Up Densities experiment (footage from Cuddleback camera traps).

Brown hyaena diet and social perceptions indicate a need for intra-guild protection

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ABSTRACT

Brown hyaenas (*Hyaena brunnea*) are poor hunters that acquire the majority of their food through scavenging [1-3]. Culpability for livestock or game losses may be misassigned to brown hyaenas if evidence of scavenging is found near carcasses, and this may provoke retaliatory actions [4]. This study examines brown hyaena diet in and around the Soutpansberg Mountains, South Africa and compares diet to social perceptions of human-hyaena conflict. Scat analysis was used to determine brown hyaena diet and to ascertain the proportion of the diet composed of domestic animals. Forty-seven mammal species and one avian species were found in the scats. Domestic animals accounted for 9.35% of all dietary occurrences. All signs suggested food acquisition through scavenging. Brown hyaena diet was strongly correlated with leopard (*Panthera pardus*) diet, and therefore it is likely that brown hyaenas are purloining much of their food from leopards. There was no correlation between brown hyaena diet and the availability of carcasses on hunting farms, nor was there a significant difference in brown hyaena diet between hunting and non-hunting seasons. Semi-structured interviews were conducted across three socio-economic groups. Most farmers tolerated predators if they demonstrated 'acceptable' behaviour. Many commercial farmers reported depredation by brown hyaenas. However this did not necessarily result in negative attitudes towards the species. Leopards were vehemently hated and this shielded brown hyaenas from much negative attention. It is predicted that if the leopard population continues to face a severe anthropogenic-induced local decline [5], this will affect brown hyaenas not only by altering their diet and potentially triggering increased consumption of domestic animals and hunting remains, but also by bringing them to the forefront of hostilities. Greater public education about brown hyaena ecology and their value to the ecosystem is recommended alongside non-lethal conflict mitigation to promote coexistence with leopards and other predators.

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Theme 2: Environmental Stressors

Expected impacts of climate change on southern African mammals

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SYNOPSIS

Under 'best case' scenarios of strenuous efforts to curb global climate change, the mean annual temperature in the interior of southern Africa will rise by the end of the 21st Century by about 3 °C above the 1960-1990 climate norm, which is already about 1.5°C above the pre-industrial temperature. In a 'worst case' scenario, where emission control efforts fail and the growth of greenhouse gases continues on the same trajectory as it has over the past half century, the southern African temperature would rise by up to 6°C relative to the 1960-1990 norm. The tendency for southern African interior temperatures to show about twice the global mean warming is confirmed in the historical record and is thought to be due to the stable presence of a descending limb of a Hadley cell over the region.

Rainfall projections are more difficult to make. The historical record shows high interannual variability, and very little trend. Models suggest a net drying in the western side of the subcontinent and a wetting on the eastern side, but disagree regarding exactly where the transition between these patterns occur. There is some evidence that the variability will increase in both cases, with a higher incidence of both severe storms and prolonged periods of drought.

Four broad approaches have been followed to convert these projections into impacts on mammals. The simplest, but least robust approach, is climatic niche modelling. It is best used for hypothesis generation, rather than prediction. More confidence can be placed in models founded in the adaptive physiology of the animal, such as their energy balance. Where the concern relates to the suitability of the habitat, its productivity and the effects mediated through other species, ecosystem modelling approaches are necessary. For slow-moving species and plants, the key problem is less the amount of climate change than its rate, and approaches based on dispersal dynamics are advocated.

On the basis of these two key sources of uncertainty - mitigation uncertainty regarding the range of future climates, and adaptation uncertainty related to how organisms will respond, four mammal-oriented scenarios are described for southern Africa in the 21st century. Most show significant disruption of community structure and function, and in the case of a combination of high climate change with low adaptive capacity, an eventual substantial loss of species.

Ecosystem impacts of Mammal extinctions and the value of Africa as the control

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SYNOPSIS

For more than a century, climate has been assumed to be the central factor driving ecosystem change. But in the last decade, there has been a rapid proliferation of new studies on biological causes of change. Central to this recent surge of interest is the question of the ecological consequences of late Pleistocene mammal extinctions. The loss of large mammals has been implicated in forest expansion, increasing tree cover in savannas, increased global fire activity, nutrient impoverishment of tropical forests, and even changes in global biogeochemical cycles between the land and the sea. Extinction of large mammals has been linked to otherwise inexplicable evolutionary anachronisms, fruits that are too big for birds, plant defences against herbivores that do not exist, and ecosystem properties rooted in the past, and not the present.

Trophic cascades as a result of extinction of top carnivores have been implicated as the causes of major changes in plants, animals and even geomorphological processes. Nearly all these studies are from the extinct lands. The only continent which still retains examples of a near intact mammal fauna is Africa. Yet the African contribution to tests of the diverse hypotheses on the consequences of megafaunal loss has been minimal. African ecologists are particularly well placed to explore the plethora of new ideas on the ecological role of mammals. In South Africa, we can compare areas with extant faunas with adjacent areas where the fauna is extinct. We are in the enviable position of running time backwards - of being able to bring mammals back to areas from which they have been lost - and observe the results. This talk will explore some of the ideas emerging from the new studies on the ecological role of the megafauna and the opportunities they provide for future research in African ecosystems.

Climate change and long-lived mammals in Africa: what the mammals are telling us

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SYNOPSIS

Whatever mitigation measures are put in place, many mammals in Africa will face a hotter and, probably more perniciously, drier environment. Projections for the fate of large mammals typically have disregarded the "stay-put" option, namely the mammals' abilities to adjust genetically or phenotypically to their altered environments. The "stay-put" option is crucial for large terrestrial mammals in Africa, because habitat fragmentation and barriers to movement will preclude many of them from shifting their range in the face of climate change. Large mammals reproduce slowly, and the rapid rate of anthropogenic climate change will preclude speciation as a means of adjusting to it. Some mammals may have the capacity for genetic adaptation by micro-evolution and by epigenetic inheritance. However, the mechanism upon which large mammals mostly will have to rely if they are to adjust to a changed environment is phenotypic plasticity. For the last 25 years, we have been exploring whether large terrestrial mammals have latent physiological talents that bring about the phenotypic changes that will be necessary. Our approach has relied on biologging, which has enabled us to measure autonomic and behavioural responses of free-living animals in their natural habitats. Importantly, data have been collected in the absence of human observers, who massively distort both the autonomic and behavioural responses of those mammals that do not habituate to human presence. To simulate what is expected under climate change, we have measured physiological responses during seasonal changes in heat and aridity in southern Africa, and we have measured physiological responses of mammals already living in environments hotter and drier than those anticipated for the next hundred years in Africa, namely the Saudi Arabian desert.

We also have assessed physiological responses in an environment in which mammals currently face bigger variations in seasonal temperature than they will in Africa (Wyoming prairie) and in an environment in which large mammals already have made an adjustment that we predict must occur in Africa, namely to switch from diurnal to nocturnal foraging (Australia). Our results imply that some large African mammals have latent talents which can be implemented phenotypically, which may ameliorate the effects of a hotter and drier environment, including important talents related to conserving body water. Our results also have made us realise the limitations of confining attention to the thermoregulatory and osmoregulatory capacities of the large mammal itself. For example, our measurements in aardvark have revealed that it is not the thermoregulatory or osmoregulatory competence of the aardvark themselves, but that of their termite and ant prey, which put the aardvark under threat. Because aardvark burrows are used by many sympatric taxa, the vulnerability of aardvark prey will compromise many other mammals, birds and reptiles too. Further, our long-term measurements of core body temperature in free-living animals have revealed that febrile illness is ubiquitous in free-living populations, leading us to endorse the view of others that immunological competence will be important in determining future persistence in the face of climate change.

Our studies also have helped to identify future research needs in the field. There has to be more experimental work of the kind that will generate relevant information, namely long-term (decade-long) studies measuring responses, autonomic and behavioural, of identified individuals, and their progeny, in populations of large mammals, living free in their natural habitats, with minimal presence of interference from humans. Only when we know how many individuals in a population have sufficient phenotypic plasticity to persist, including reproducing, in their altered environment can we make predictions regarding the persistence of the population, and ultimately the species. Those studies cannot be confined to single species, but must be of trophic cascades, and those mammals that have key roles in ecosystems need special attention. Such studies are difficult to carry out, require multidisciplinary teams, and require long-term commitments by conservation authorities, land-owners, and funders. We also have realised the need for much closer collaboration between physiologists and ecologists. That interdisciplinary collaboration is crucial if we are combine what physiologists know about individual animals with what ecologists know about communities, to better predict the persistence of populations and communities under future climate change.

Towards a mammalian umbrella: Sustaining synergies and scholastic opportunities

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SYNOPSIS

South Africa possesses a rich and abundant source of material for research on the evolution and fate of African mammals. For example, the fossil record of Permian and Triassic mammals from the Karoo Basin is unsurpassed in the world. However, research and teaching trends at South African universities pose alarming threats to the persistence of integrated mammalogy. Most critically, university posts for mammalogists are either being frozen or they are being filled by academics with unrelated interests. Thus countrywide the number of mammalogists is declining and so too are the number of postgraduate research students in the discipline.

Ironically, the decline in expertise in mammalogy comes at a time when the prospects for meaningful synergies and a more integrative approach to mammalogy are better than ever. The potential is made possible by the increased knowledge of the evolutionary linkages between the specialities in mammalogy, including disciplines such as mammal palaeontology. Sustaining and strengthening a national centre of excellence for mammal research has therefore become essential for the preservation and future scholastic potential and opportunities in mammalogy. Such a centre needs to take an integrative approach and renewed ownership of mammalogy under a broad conceptual mammalian 'umbrella' that can ensure equitable funding across sub-disciplines.

At present, the predominant research on mammals in South Africa focuses heavily on contemporary threats to the persistence of mammals. These efforts are admirable and understandable given the very real threats involved. Moreover, these efforts are able to attract more funding than, for example, pure evolutionary research. However, a mammalian umbrella needs to cover more than contemporary issues; it demands a strong evolutionary emphasis to bind together the mammalian specialities, for example morphology, physiology, behaviour, biochemistry, microbiology, phylogenetics and parasitology, that have tended to become increasingly isolated in response to the exponential increase in information content. A mammalian centre of excellence must also have the willingness to resist pressures, especially political, that can dilute these sub-disciplines.

Expanding research to the past, for example the knowledge of past climatic and environmental perturbations associated with the evolution of mammals, is critical for predicting meaningful persistence scenarios. Increased national and international synergy with disciplines such as palaeontology and evolutionary biology must endeavour to reconstruct mammalian traits that evolved over the 300 million years of mammalian evolution. The contemporary tools of evolutionary biology make it possible today to see into the past - to reconstruct the traits of extinct mammals - and to discern patterns in the course of their evolution. Here I provide examples of how this approach has been used to better understand the relationships between extinct and extant mammals, as well as the evolution of endothermy, metabolic rate, body temperature, heterothermy (torpor and hibernation), the scrotum (spermatogenesis), and the locomotor energetics of mammals.

Mediating climate change and human wellbeing: On the value chain of mammal research

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SYNOPSIS

Climate change is a phenomenon that directly influences mammal research through a number of pathways:

First, mammal community structure and distribution is a function of the climate context of the past - from long-term evolutionary dynamics that operate on the multi-million year time scale, through to short-term responses that manifests as behavioural adaptations to uneven resource distribution within the lifetime of an individual. Reconstruction of past climate in southern Africa has demonstrated that the main long-term ecological driver (climate) has not been a static entity that was abruptly and rudely interrupted by the industrial revolution, and as a result has suddenly entered a period of uncharacteristic flux. Instead the natural climate variability has been somewhat fickle. The 2015/16 summer rainfall drought over southern Africa was brought about by a strong El Nino event, and it patently exerted a strong ecological force. The record for the last 1000 years shows that El Nino is a persistent component in the climate system, but despite the apparent severity of the El Nino/La Nina cycle, there have been events that exceed it both in terms of magnitude, and duration. What occurred in the past were not a series of gradual, processual changes as future climate change is mistakenly considered to be. Instead they were abrupt regime shifts with little or no warning of what was to come. The impact is that certain triggers in the climate system bring about changes that might mimic El Nino, but persist for decades rather than a season or two. The current state of ecological systems is therefore not a steady state phenomenon to be characterised and described in static terms, but rather a particular state of a dynamic system in which mammal adaptation is likely sub-optimal.

Second, mammals, like all other components of ecological systems, will be subject to ecological forcing brought about by future climate change. The problem is that future climate change is uncharted territory in which predictions match or exceed the most extreme climate change events of the recent past. Patently the ecological functioning to which we are accustomed has evolved through a history of climate change, but in the process it has not necessarily been congenial to optimal mammal (and particularly human) functioning.

Third is the policy domain. Climate change has become one of the most important phenomenon driving policy formulation from the global through to the local level. International policy presents a guideline for local policy under the banner of sustainable development, and this includes provision around issue such as ecosystem services, and conservation of biodiversity. Navigating the policy framework reveals a very important aspect that must be woven into the future fabric of mammal research. That is: sustainability is predicated by the interactions between economic, social and ecological systems. This is particularly acute when the South African policy framework is considered. Research funding came under close scrutiny following the 1996 publication of the White Paper on Science and Technology. In this, the research capacity in South Africa was couched in the National System of Innovation, and the emphasis on Innovation meant that funding streams from the public sector would focus on tangible outcomes. The system has matured and the publication of the Innovation towards a Knowledge-Based Economy policy by the Department of Science and Technology (2008) is very prescriptive about the alignment of public sector research funding with the national priorities. Local and international policy frameworks will surely inform the nature of future mammal research.

Phenomenology, or the kind of basic observations that characterise the Age of Discovery are unlikely to attract funding when competing against research that clearly articulates a contribution to overarching or higher level objectives. In South Africa, and probably beyond, it is clear that the human state is the dominant theme - sustainability is not an altruistic desire to preserve ecosystems (or mammal species) for their intrinsic state of being - but rather a selfish desire to preserve or improve the wellbeing of people. The social indicators for South Africa portray a dire need that cannot justify phenomenological research. Instead all research needs to explore the value chain between the phenomenology and the human state. In this respect the decolonization of research, that is finding traction in South Africa, demands that any investment needs to meet a social mandate that is locally defined. The apparent contradiction between local social imperatives and global value in biodiversity needs to be reconciled in future mammal research.

Climate change presents a potential hook that captures the value chain of mammal research. Many parts of southern Africa are sub-optimal for agriculture and pastoralism, and mammals (wildlife) represent a viable alternative (in terms of a value continuum from tourism to hunting). The southern Africa climate change scenario is likely to see expansion of the arid west, severe impacts of biodiversity hotspots such as the Okavango, and a likely reduction in economically viable land-use. Rainfall changes will cause population and human migration that will bring about increased demand for resources at a time that ecosystem services will be declining. In this context the adaptation of wildlife becomes a tenable form of primary productivity on which the people in southern Africa will come to rely.

A critical aspect of this future is that mammal research needs to elevate phenomenological observations and ensure that they integrate through high level thinking with socio-economic systems. In doing so the understanding of ecosystem services needs

to become a prominent voice in policy formulation regarding climate change at all levels. Success with such lofty political (policy) objectives requires broad scale integration with fields such as social development and economics. Climate change also has a large spatial scale. The emphasis on socio-economic systems interfaced with mammal research leads to a solution that not only addresses a South African need, but also regional imperative.

Population dynamics and distribution of large herbivores in a spatially changing world

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SYNOPSIS

Animals respond to temporally variable environments by exploiting spatial heterogeneity in resources, risks and conditions at various scales. Compression of the spatial scope for adaptive responses and homogenization of conditions locally constitute major threats to ultimate population viability. Many protected areas established to conserve Africa's megafauna may fail to achieve this objective in the near future due to their effective downsizing in the context of expanding human populations and land transformations, coupled with climate shifts. Findings from my own and other research illustrating the importance of spatial considerations include (1) regional counterbalancing of the local impacts of mega-herbivores like elephants and rhinos for other species; (2) habitat suitability dependent on seasonal phenology of local vegetation resources for browsing kudus; (3) population contraction through local herd extirpation of sable antelope; (4) exposure to predation mediated through apparent competition determining regional distribution of rarer antelope; (5) spatial extent of habitat sufficiently secure from predation governing abundance of wildebeest; (6) locally changing exploitation of resources within vast overall ranges by arid zone ungulates; (7) imminent extinctions of localized smaller ungulates within Hluhluwe-Mfolozi; (8) declining trends of major prey species in Hluhluwe-Mfolozi under predation. Models projecting population dynamics must accommodate spatial changes in environments in order to reliably anticipate future population trends. Adaptively effective responses can be represented drawing on concepts of state-dependent fitness. Advances in GPS telemetry and remotely sensed imagery open new opportunities to address spatial issues provided sufficient funding can be mobilized to adequately represent populations.

Reproductive cooperation and environmental stress

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SUMMARY

Cooperation is as pervasive in biological systems as competition but its evolutionary causes and ecological consequences are still debated. The most highly developed and costly forms of cooperation involve cooperation between individuals to rear young and (both among birds and among mammals) systems where dependent juveniles are reared by non-breeding helpers are commonly associated with environments where annual rainfall is low and unpredictable. Experimental and correlational evidence shows that helpers increase rates of recruitment and cooperative breeding may have evolved in species living in unpredictable habitats because it minimises the risk that lineages will become extinct under adverse environmental conditions.

Cooperative breeding systems have other important consequences. They generate high levels of fecundity, high variance in breeding success between females and intense competition between them as well as unusual adaptations favouring competitive ability in females. In many species, these are associated with the suppression of reproduction in subordinate females throughout part or all of their lifespans. In addition, cooperative breeders commonly show positive correlations between group size and recruitment which may retard rates of population recovery from droughts and epidemics. Recent papers have suggested that humans evolved as cooperative breeders - but this seems unlikely as the evolution of cooperative breeding (the rearing of offspring by non-breeding helpers) appears to have been restricted to monogamous, polytocous animals that lived in groups with high average relatedness between group members.

THOUGHTS FOR THE FUTURE

Over the last fifty years, as the techniques of ecological research have developed and the aims of research projects have become increasingly well defined, the aims of applied and fundamental research have become increasingly separate. This process is likely to continue and it is sensible to recognise and adapt to this trend. One solution is to identify areas of biological research where the requirements of applied and fundamental research coincide. One of these is the maintenance of long-term ecological data[1-3]. Most important ecological changes (including responses to climate change and habitat loss) occur over multiple decades and accurate measurement of sequential changes are often necessary to allow ecological processes to be understood and future changes to be predicted[2,3].

While some ecological questions can be answered using cross-sectional demographic data, individual-based studies where recognisable animals are monitored throughout their lives can be the only way to measure some important processes (such as the frequency and extent of dispersal), and studies that have access to records of this kind often provide crucial insights into the mechanisms responsible for changes in population density and distribution[4]. Long-term, individual-based studies are of central importance in areas of biology, including evolutionary biology, animal behaviour, population genetics and environmental physiology and much of our understanding of animal breeding systems and reproductive adaptations are based on a relatively small number of long-term field studies that have been able to track the life-histories of large samples of individuals[5].

One consequence of the opportunities provided by long-term, individual-based field studies is that they are often able to attract collaborators and funding from across a wide range of disciplines. While South Africa is already a base for several distinguished long-term studies of vertebrates, there are opportunities for many more – though careful thought needs to be given to identify suitable species and optimal study sites. Ideal species are visible, catchable, possible subjects for field and lab experiments, not too long long-lived and not endangered[4].

There would also be substantial benefits in establishing a central repository of long-term biological and ecological data, incorporating both individual-based demographic data from detailed field studies, demographic data from population-level studies and long-term records of species distributions. A centralised database of this kind could be used by scientists to explore comparisons and contrasts between species in their responses to ecological change and to compare the responses of different categories of plant and animal populations. Synthetic studies of this kind based on long-term data are now emerging in Europe and North America (eg[3,6]), and South Africa would be well placed to bring together data sets of this kind – initially for studies based in South Africa itself and subsequently for studies based elsewhere in the continent.

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Determinants of the effectiveness of African protected areas at conserving lions and their prey

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SYNOPSIS

Research insights:

With surveys of experts associated with 186 sites across 24 countries, we assessed the effectiveness of African protected areas (PAs) at conserving lions and their prey, identified factors that influence conservation effectiveness, and identified patterns in the severity of various threats. Less than one third of sampled PAs conserve lions at ~50% of their estimated carrying capacity (K), and less than half conserve lion prey species at ~50% of K. Given adequate management, PAs could theoretically support >4x the total extant population of wild African lions (~83,000), providing a measurable benchmark for future conservation efforts. The performance of PAs shows marked geographic variation, and in several countries there is a need for a significant elevation in conservation effort. Bushmeat poaching was identified as the most serious threat to both lions and to wildlife in general. The severity of threats to wildlife in PAs was best predicted by geographic and socioeconomic variables, related to the size, position, and shape of PAs, local human densities and national economic indicators. However, conservation outcomes for lions and their prey were best explained by management variables. PAs tend to be more effective for conserving lions and their prey where management budgets were higher, in privately owned reserves, where photographic tourism is the primary land use, and in the case of prey, where fencing was present. Lions and prey fared less well in poorer countries, where people were settled within PAs, in higher rainfall regions and where PA's were used for neither trophy hunting or tourism.

Recommended priority actions:

Africa's protected area network faces severe and growing challenges from human pressures, and particularly encroachment with people and livestock and various forms of poaching. At the same time, the resources available to manage protected areas frequently fall far short of what is necessary, leaving them extremely vulnerable to overexploitation. As a result, a high and growing proportion of African protected areas are becoming depleted of wildlife. As prey species disappear, large carnivores follow. To rectify this situation, there is a need for a significant elevation in financial support for protected areas, both from African governments in some cases, and from the international community. There is a strong case for greater support for African conservation efforts from the international community. First, the demand for wildlife products that drives poaching is at least partly international in nature. The developed world derives benefit from the existence value associated with African megafauna, and the ecosystem services from African PAs, without bearing the associated costs. Several African countries have vast PA networks that are far larger than the international average (as a % of their land area). Developed countries have not once fulfilled their obligations for support for conservation in the tropics made at the 1992 Rio Earth Summit. Lastly, investment in protected areas can yield economic growth, economic diversification, poverty relief and job creation in remote rural areas in a way that traditional donor aid rarely delivers. Support for African protected areas is most likely to be effective if it is set up as long term technical and financial support or as official co-management of protected areas.

Priorities for research Africa is facing a biological crisis. Large mammal populations are declining in both abundance and distribution in many parts of the continent. Many African countries are losing their wildlife before they ever have chance to benefit from the resource. Other aspects of biodiversity are also under severe pressure due to a suite of threats. We need to find solutions to address these challenges, urgently. The days where we can afford study wildlife while it disappears around us are gone. In my opinion, the Mammal Research Institute needs to fulfil the following roles. Firstly, the emphasis of research and primary focus of the MRI should shift significantly towards finding practical solutions for the conservation crisis unfolding on the continent. Secondly, the MRI should become a training hub to help produce top quality African scientists, particularly from within the state wildlife authorities to help capacitate those vital institutions. Thirdly, the MRI should strive to attract high quality international students, as a means of both raising the profile of the institution and of generating financial resources to help subsidize the training of African students from poorer backgrounds.

Monitoring environmental stress: current and future perspectivesR.P. Millar (robertpetermillar@gmail.com)

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ABSTRACT

Adaptation to changes in the environment is essential for survival of species. The adaptive process demands considerable physiological and behavioural adjustments with accompanying stress and recruitment of allostatic adjustment before return to homeostasis. Changes in external (eg temperature, infection, nutrition and water availability) and internal (eg fat, carbohydrate and protein stores, hormones, inflammatory and growth factors) are detected in the brain and integrated in the hypothalamus and translated into changed neuropeptide secretion and downstream pituitary secretion. These give rise to behavioural, metabolic, thermoregulatory, electrolyte/water, reproductive, thyroid and adrenal changes. Monitoring these changes has the potential to assist in management practice especially in situations of potential population crashes and for threatened species.

A major stress accommodating pathway is the hypothalamic (CRF)/pituitary (ACTH)/adrenal (cortisol) pathway which has important survival benefits when activated acutely. Chronic stress and activation of the HPA axis has detrimental effects through a catabolic state and suppression of the immune system. Distinguishing these two states is crucial when assessing chronic stress in wildlife. The most common methodology directed at this is that of cortisol and metabolite monitoring by immunoassays in fecal samples. While this has been effective there are severe limitations and new approaches and technologies with improved differential diagnostic capabilities are emerging and likely to be employed in the next two decades. These include the specific and simultaneous monitoring of individual steroids and metabolites by high throughput mass spectrometry, monitoring surrogate pathways such as the hypothalamic/pituitary/gonadal axis which is very sensitive to increased stress, monitoring of novel biomarkers such as C Reactive Protein which sensitively responds to inflammatory conditions and is highly conserved in species, and in seeking sensitive and specific novel cortisol responsive genes which may be better indicators and discriminators of chronic stress.

Drought: individual responses and their effect on group, and population level changesDavid Gaynor^{1,2}, Helen Spence-Jones², Christopher Duncan², Jack Thorley^{3,2}, Marta Manser^{4,2} and Tim Clutton-Brock^{1,2,3} (dgaynor@iafrica.com)¹Mammal Research Institute, University of Pretoria cnr Lynnwood Road and Roper Street, Hatfield, South Africa²Kalahari Meerkat Project, Kuruman River reserve, Van Zylsrus, Northern Cape, South Africa³Zoology Department, University of Cambridge, Downing St., Cambridge, CB2 3EJ, United Kingdom ⁴Department of Evolutionary Biology and Environmental Studies, University of Zurich, Winterthurerstrasse 190, 8057, Zurich, Switzerland**ABSTRACT**

Drought is the predominant environmental stressor in Sub-Saharan Africa. Prolonged and more frequent droughts are likely to be the most pervasive effect of long term human induced climate change in Southern Africa. Despite there being a large literature on decline in mammal populations during drought there is very little published on individual responses to drought. Droughts can typically reduce terrestrial mammal populations by 75%. Which individuals survive droughts and reproduce subsequent to the drought is consequently important to recovery/survival of the population and what genotypes are maintained in the population. Here we present: 1) fine temporal scale data of the effects of a recent drought in the Kalahari (2015/2016) on different individuals in a population of meerkats and 2) long-term results based on 22 years of data on which what factors influenced individual meerkat survival during six droughts that occurred during this study period. Extended drought saw a high decline in weight and body condition, increased pup mortality and cessation of breeding in that order. Pup birth weight, and weight at first foraging was lower however age at which pups started foraging with the groups was not different from other years. There was no immediate effect during the drought on adult mortality, despite adults losing all fat reserves. Mortality in droughts was not random and the effect of drought varied with sex, age and social status. Dominant breeding females seem to be buffered from the effects of drought. Our results suggest that, especially in socially structured populations, it is important not just to know the numbers of animals lost or surviving a drought, but to have an understanding of what underpins the change in numbers in terms of individual characteristics such as sex, age, dominance and size as this can have an effect on the structure and resilience of the population.

Fig. 1. (a) Kalahari meerkats in good years (b) Contrasts between drought years and good years in the Kalahari

From daring to dependable: field methods for detecting change within long-term studies

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ABSTRACT

Detecting environmental change requires adequate methods that accurately measure features of the system of interest. Measuring these features in long-term research studies allows for the detection of change. Methods used for long term research need to be appropriate and rigorous. Complex and varied problems result in uncertainty leading to the wrong choice of method or using methods that are out-dated but still popular. Long term field methods should capture data that can meet the assumptions and demands of rapidly evolving analytical techniques. As an example, I use a unique, uninterrupted and continuing long-term large mammal research programme that illustrates field methodology that is both bold and reserved. The data are used to answer a range of population ecology questions. The Marion Island southern elephant seal *Mirounga leonina* population has been scrutinised intensively for 33 years to establish causes for historical population decline and more recent stabilisation. This long term mark-recapture experiment relies on the flipper tagging of all pups born on the island. This simple and dependable methodology has generated 33 years of unparalleled data to address ecological questions and detect change. Although simple in theory, foresight and careful planning are needed to sustain this effort. In practice the resighting of >11000 seals at weekly intervals for 33 years along a Subantarctic coastline of ~80km, requires significant manpower, dedication and financial investment. Conversely, a daring methodological experiment was developed to overcome immediate practical impediments to gathering simple augmenting data for demographic analysis. Elephant seals are difficult to physically weigh, but body condition provides a critical covariate for demographic modelling. Despite scepticism and practical hindrances, we developed a three-dimensional photogrammetric method to accurately "weigh" 3500kg seals. This technologically advanced field method collects body condition data that provides a measure of individual success. I present examples of field methodology ranging from daring to dependable, to inspire the young mammalogists to be both innovative but also conservative in their efforts to answer questions of environmental change.

Killer whale research at South Africa's sub-Antarctic Prince Edward Islands: a globally significant cetacean research programme in the making

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ABSTRACT

Since South Africa's first scientific expeditions to the Prince Edward Islands, killer whales (*Orcinus orca*) have interested biologists at the islands. Early reports [1] noted the regular presence of killer whales inshore at the islands. From the 1970s to the early 2000s, largely opportunistic observations, including photographs allowing the identification of individuals, described a population of killer whales which regularly returned to the islands in small groups (~3 individuals) to hunt seals and penguins [2, 3]. A more dedicated effort to observe and photograph recognizable individuals was initiated in 2006, leading to a preliminary glimpse into the social organization of killer whales there [4]. Subsequently, an intensive photographic mark-recapture effort was launched [5], allowing individuals to be tracked through time, and the consideration of the role of killer whales as apex predators in sub-Antarctic ecosystems [6]. These individual histories, coupled with satellite telemetry, stable isotope, genetic, and social structure analyses, have begun to reveal the ecology of killer whales at Marion Island, including findings which are shifting perspectives on killer whale ecology. The latest work has shown long-range movements alternated with inshore hunting and following fishing vessels to steal fish; deep diving which is linked to the unexpectedly broad diet also suggested by stable isotope analysis; and a dynamic social organization of small, somewhat fluid social groups comprising kin as well as non-kin [7, 8]. The individual identification dataset is now a decade old, and will soon allow uniquely detailed demographic analyses. The programme overall is poised to become a globally significant cetacean research project.

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Acoustic monitoring of the recovery of blue and fin whales in the Benguela ecosystem

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ABSTRACT

Numerous large baleen whales were whaled to near extinction in the South Atlantic Ocean; however, little is known about their recovery, distribution, behaviour and migration four decades after whaling terminated. Passive acoustic monitoring technology was used to detect blue and fin whale calls to investigate their seasonal presence and behavior in the Benguela ecosystem. Data were collected using an autonomous acoustic recorder (at a sample rate of 4 kHz for a minimum of 20 minutes every hour of each day) attached to oceanographic moorings, deployed for 17 months off the West Coast of South Africa between 2014 and 2015. Our results show that migratory blue and fin whales are predominantly present in South African waters between May and August with some animals extending their presence to November. Antarctic blue whales were observed to produce both their characteristic Z-call and the feeding produced D-calls with totals of 8716 and 176 Z- and D-calls detected, and might be indicative of the blue whale population size increase. The detected 56503 fin whale calls also suggest a potentially recovering whale population. Both whale species were more vocally active during day. Here we present the first acoustic recordings of Antarctic blue whales in the Southeast Atlantic Ocean, highlighting importance of monitoring Antarctic top consumer baleen whales in the low latitudes, and provide preliminary information on which to concentrate further research effort to investigate abundance, distribution and seasonality of large baleen whale populations in the Benguela system.

Do low recruitment and growth rates preclude tall trees from landscapes with elephants?

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ABSTRACT

The potential for elephants to negatively impact biodiversity in protected areas remains a concern for both conservation managers and tourists. Most concerns arise from observations of the loss of tall trees in areas where elephant densities are high. Perceived negative impacts range from the loss of aesthetically-pleasing landscapes, to the loss of fauna which depend on tall trees. Despite decades of concerns and research[1], it remains unclear whether wildlife areas can support both unregulated elephant populations and a desirable density of tall trees. A critical knowledge gap is the

demography of the tree species involved. If these species cannot recruit and grow fast enough to replace tall trees felled by elephant, then even low densities of elephants will eventually eliminate tall trees from a landscape. To address this gap, monitoring of tall tree species was initiated at 7 savanna sites in the central Lowveld. Six years of annual sampling revealed low rates of recruitment and growth (Fig. 1). However, high densities of saplings, combined with maximum growth rates, indicate the possibility of sustaining a population of tall trees. A simple model was created to explore what density of tall trees could coexist with elephants, given the current rates of tall tree loss[2] for one of the study sites within the Kruger National Park. The probability of sub- adult trees being severely damaged by elephant emerged as a critical variable, as did the density of juvenile trees. These results elucidate a conundrum for some managers, in terms of solving concurrent problems of bush encroachment and tall tree loss. They also indicate that monitoring elephant densities is of little value unless combined with monitoring the fate of sub-adult trees. Finally, they raise interesting questions regarding how tall tree species and elephants co-existed in pre-colonial times, when elephant densities were higher.

Fig. 1. Height growth rates for three tall tree species at a study site near Phalaborwa in the Kruger National Park.

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Sexual segregation in a large African ungulate: contrasting habitat use, predation risk and diel activity patterns

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the drivers of sexual segregation in ungulates has received considerable attention, with the majority of evidence for such behaviour coming from northern temperate regions [1]. In contrast, research on African ungulates has focused predominantly at the population level [but see 2,3]. African ecosystems, however, provide ideal opportunities to test competing theories of sexual segregation because they are heterogeneous, harbour a wide variety of sexually dimorphic species and contain a full suite of large predators. Using data from camera traps (n = 67 sites), Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) and GPS collared lions *Panthera leo*; we investigated a novel approach to assess the potential drivers of segregation between male, mixed adult and breeding groups of eland *Tragelaphus oryx* in Addo Elephant National Park. Our results suggest that eland group segregation patterns are similar to those observed in buffalo *Syncerus caffer* [3]; where adult males tolerate greater levels of predation risk than females. We further show that although female dominated groups minimized predation risk, female groups with dependent young were hyper-sensitive to predation risk in both time and space. With current declines in large ungulate populations occurring globally [4], conservation actions need to be guided by relevant population and demographic data, including accurate predator-prey models. Including relative prey vulnerability in predator-prey models [5] highlights the importance of understanding such vulnerabilities at a sub-population level. Our research seeks to elevate the importance of understanding demographic differences in prey vulnerability and habitat use in African ecosystems to levels observed in research on northern temperate ungulates.

Fig. 1. Camera trap images depicting an (a) adult male eland group and (b) an eland breeding group. Group identity was confirmed using multiple pictures obtained from the independent eland detection events.

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The possible role of epigenetics in mammalian wildlife adaptation to changing environments

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ABSTRACT

Understanding animal responses to the rapidly changing natural world is of vital importance to management and conservation practises. The emerging use of genomics has provided a promising avenue into this field, specifically relating to evolutionary potential [1]. Furthermore the burgeoning field of ecological epigenetics may provide insight into mammalian wildlife phenotypic variation arising from non-genetic sources [1-3]. Epigenetic mechanisms have been shown to increase population flexibility to allow for adaptation to rapidly changing environmental conditions [4]. Better insight into these mechanisms and their relative contribution to evolutionary potential in mammalian wildlife may provide an exciting possibility for ecological, evolutionary and conservation genomic applications. Epigenetic mechanisms such as DNA methylation can be studied using techniques such as methylation-sensitive amplified fragment length polymorphism (MS-AFLP) to identify and characterize environmentally induced epigenetic variations in mammalian wildlife populations [5]. Alternative methods (e.g. array-based methods, [6]) are also available for identifying individuals or wild populations with the greatest potential to adapt rapidly to changing environmental conditions, via the characterization of epigenetic variation [2]. Transgenerational epigenetic variation may further aid the study of long term, heritable variations in phenotypes outside of the DNA sequence, potentially acting as a buffer for populations exposed to rapidly changing environments [1,2,7]. The field of ecological epigenetics thus provides an exciting opportunity for fields such as genetics, evolutionary biology and ecology to collaborate to enhance our understanding of adaptation and plasticity in the face of a rapidly changing natural world.

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Digging for answers: contributions of density- and frequency- dependent factors on ectoparasite burden in a social mammal

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ABSTRACT

Common patterns in parasite ecology are difficult to find, as the distribution of parasites amongst hosts can be influenced by several abiotic (e.g. rainfall, temperature) and biotic factors (e.g. host sex, breeding condition and sociality) simultaneously. Several studies have indicated that variation in ectoparasite loads of small mammal populations are primarily due to environmental fluctuations. However, it is unknown whether these patterns are retained in subterranean habitats, where individuals are protected from extremes of ambient conditions. This study aimed to answer this question by analysing ectoparasites of common mole-rats (*Cryptomys hottentotus hottentotus*). Samples were collected seasonally from populations inhabiting both an arid and a mesic area along the western coast of South Africa. Effects of environmental (location, rainfall, temperature) and host-related factors (sex, breeding status, group size) on ectoparasite abundance were assessed. Only five parasite species from three taxa were found all of which were more abundant in the wet season possibly due to increases in host dispersal. In contrast, both species richness and abundance were greater at the arid site. The effects of biotic factors differed between ectoparasite taxa probably as a result of different life-history strategies of the different taxa. For the most common parasites (*Androlaelaps* spp.) the abundance decreased significantly with group size. These results defy the consensus that gregarious behaviour is costly in terms of parasite infestation and suggest that environmental factors may affect ectoparasites of subterranean host both directly and indirectly.

Theme 3: Diseases at the interface

Policy options for wildlife, livelihoods and transboundary animal disease management in southern Africa

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SYNOPSIS

On May 27th 2015, the World Organization for Animal Health (OIE), which provides standards for its 180 member countries related to international trade in commodities (including beef) that are a potential source of animal disease agents, updated the OIE Terrestrial Animal Health Code and made it possible for African countries with wild species like buffalo that naturally harbor foot and mouth disease viruses to be able to trade beef without necessarily requiring the physical separation of wildlife and livestock through the extensive veterinary cordon fencing that has characterized animal disease management in southern Africa since the colonial era. This policy change offers the unprecedented possibility of access to new beef markets for southern African farmers as well as unlocks the potential for restoring migratory movements of wildlife and thus enhancing prospects for long-term wildlife population viability within individual countries as well as across vast southern African transfrontier conservation areas (TFCAs), including the Kavango Zambezi TFCA spanning Angola, Botswana, Namibia, Zambia and Zimbabwe and home to the world's largest remaining population of elephants- approximately 250,000.

To make progress on the momentum gained thus far, ongoing efforts need to focus on:

1. Sensitizing government and private sector stakeholders to new approaches to disease risk management that don't rely on landscape-fragmenting fencing;
2. Providing technical assistance and training on the applicability of agricultural value-chain approaches that complement wildlife-compatible land uses instead of preclude them; and
3. Informing cross-sectoral policy responses that support sustainable conservation, system health and resilience, and economic development - all as underpinned by stewardship of a healthy land base.

Disease and protected area resilience: an exploration of future scenarios for southern Africa

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SYNOPSIS

Protected areas form the core of efforts to conserve biological diversity. In southern Africa they are particularly important for the protection and conservation of large mammals and make a significant contribution to the regional economy. Protected areas (PAs) are embedded in larger landscapes with diverse land uses, cultures, and jurisdictions. As such they are fundamentally complex social-ecological systems driven by both ecological and socio-economic dynamics at different levels and scales.

The resilience of PAs can be thought of as their ability to maintain key elements of their identity through space and time in response to various perturbations and changes. Identity of PAs is linked to their stated aims as decided upon by society, the range of species and habitats that an area is expected to conserve, and the ecosystem and social services that it provides.

Nature-based tourism, which is largely based on wild large charismatic mammals, contributes more to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in southern Africa than domestic livestock despite the latter forming 90% of the large herbivore biomass in the region. The resilience of southern African PAs to shocks and disturbance is therefore important to both conservation and national and regional economies. While many of the major factors directly impacting the resilience of protected areas are socio-economic, the potential impact of disease is seldom considered and is explored in the following scenarios. While direct major impacts of disease on wildlife in protected areas may be rare, the indirect impacts of disease on socio-economic drivers of PA resilience may be substantial. As a result diseases may contribute to generating regime shifts and undesirable change in the identity of PAs and transfrontier conservation areas.

A brief outline of the current distribution and status of protected areas and transfrontier conservation areas in southern Africa is presented as background to exploring the following scenarios (i.e. plausible alternative futures) relating to disease and PA social-ecological system resilience in southern Africa.

- * A continuation of the status quo, business as usual and likely surprises in disease interface dynamics
- * Rapid rural human population growth and the expansion of smallholder / subsistence farming resulting in increasing habitat fragmentation, isolation of PAs, altered wildlife/livestock/human disease interfaces and conflict.
- * Rapid industrialisation, rural to urban migration, reduced human wildlife interface and conflict, but increasing urban dominance of protected area management and anti-sustainable use of wild mammals resulting in habitat change and disease dynamics within PAs.
- * Climate change impacts on protected areas and diseases.

In conclusion, the implications for research on disease (pathogens and parasites) at the interface will be outlined.

Disease at the wildlife / livestock interface: the challenge to harmonize wildlife conservation and human livelihoods in the GLTFCA context

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SYNOPSIS

The establishment of the Great Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Area in 2001 was a pioneering and big step forward for conservation in southern Africa. The fundamental goal of the initiative was to allow greater movement of wildlife across larger landscapes thereby allowing ecosystem processes to play out in as natural a state as possible. The initiative also acknowledged that people are part of the system and that the establishment of a peace park can and will create opportunities for people to improve their livelihoods.

The removal of fences and encouragement of wildlife to recolonize areas where they formerly occurred - either through translocation or natural migration - has both had positive and negative effects. Wildlife populations have been able to become more resilient to changing environments through establishment of population pockets over a greater area but these wildlife movements have inadvertently moved certain unwanted pathogens with them. Contact between wildlife and livestock have increased and has the potential of transferring diseases to livestock and also livestock diseases to wildlife.

SANParks and its partners (including the Skukuza State Veterinary Office) have invested significantly in understanding disease impact and prevalence within the Kruger National Park. Our understanding has improved significantly and we recognise that disease plays an important role in population health regulation but rarely threatens population persistence. The emphasis more recently has shifted to work closely with veterinary and conservation authorities in Mozambique and Zimbabwe to better understand potential disease transmission risks between livestock and wildlife.

With decreasing investment and resources going into traditional veterinary controls in all three countries it has become imperative to investment into understanding the risk and impact of disease transmission to be able to manage the risks locally and in a non-geographic approach (as opposed to conventional Foot & Mouth Disease Zoning).

There are great opportunities in the GLTFCA for people, their livestock and wildlife to co-exist if the interface issues, including disease, are managed innovatively and at a local scale. Global environmental change will result in significant changes and challenges to the environment and only in resilient heterogeneous systems will populations, especially specialised species, be able to persist.

Vision:

Future disease research will take place in a multidisciplinary arena where risk of disease transmission is better understood so that innovative but practical interventions can be introduced to reduce risk of disease transmission both to livestock and wildlife. This understanding will allow greater opportunities for wildlife and people with their livestock to co-exist. Ecosystem resilience and improved livelihood need to be encouraged through interdisciplinary management and integrated land use systems, underpinned by practical, management based research.

Infectious disease threats to wild mammals in southern Africa: risks at intra- and interspecies interfaces

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SYNOPSIS

Infectious pathogens present threats to humans, domestic animals, and wildlife. These diseases result in morbidity and mortality of individuals, alter populations, have socioeconomic and trade consequences, present zoonotic risks, and have an impact on conservation activities. The typical infectious disease paradigm depicts the spread of a pathogen from a reservoir host through a variety of routes to a susceptible host. However, this scenario does not take into account the complex network of factors that influence transmission and disease outcome. The jigsaw puzzle involves environmental, pathogen, and host factors. When a pathogen can infect multiple species, the complexity is compounded by the unique response of each species to the existing conditions.

Some infectious diseases in animals are emerging or re-emerging. The World Health Organization defines an emerging disease as "one that has appeared in a population for the first time, or that may have existed previously but is rapidly increasing in incidence or geographic range." A growing list of global emerging diseases are zoonotic (i.e. are transmitted between animals and humans). There are numerous reasons that emerging diseases are increasing, including climatic changes and weather extremes; changes in land use, fragmentation and loss of habitat; war, civil unrest, and movement of displaced persons; human encroachment and urbanization; increase in rapid transport, trade, and bushmeat; and cross species transmission of infectious pathogens. The threat of interspecies transmission of diseases at interfaces is demonstrated by numerous examples of pathogens that can infect a range of hosts, especially in small fragmented and endangered populations. Often the impact of these diseases on wildlife are unknown. Morbidity can increase the risk of predation, affect hunting ability, and have reproductive and social hierarchy effects. Mortality can lead to loss of genetic diversity and even local extinctions. Infectious diseases may disrupt conservation programs due to limits on translocations of animals and the risk of inadvertent spread of disease to naïve populations. There are also socioeconomic consequences with loss of tourism, hunting, and condemnation of animal products.

The recent outbreaks of canine distemper virus in African wildlife highlights concerns about emerging infectious diseases. In 1994, over 1000 lions and uncounted hyenas, bat-eared foxes, and leopards died in Tanzania from CDV. In 2009, 4 lion mortalities were associated with CDV in the Kgalagadi. Several packs of Ethiopian wolves became extinct in 2010 due to disease. In South Africa, there was a severe outbreak in domestic dogs in the Port Elizabeth area during 2015, and subsequently there have been 4 wildlife outbreaks in 2016 (lions in Limpopo, wild dogs in Kalahari, Kruger, and Hluhluwe). In addition to the direct impact of disease, the risk of transmission from wildlife reservoirs can be a source of human-wildlife conflict. Pathogen spillover from wildlife to livestock can exacerbate poverty in rural communities due to morbidity/mortality of cattle, and loss of access to grazing lands and water resources. Diseases such as Foot-and-Mouth Disease, Corridor disease, heartwater, Brucellosis, and Nagana may not have significant effects on wildlife populations but can result in devastating outcomes for surrounding livestock. Similarly, domestic animal pathogens present threats to wildlife. Over 77% of cattle pathogens are considered multi-host diseases. Increased interfaces result in exposure to novel pathogens and "emerging" disease in wildlife populations.

There are a number of examples of important infectious diseases at human-domestic animal-wildlife interfaces in South Africa. Rabies is an acute viral disease that can affect any mammal including humans. Domestic dogs are the natural host, although global wildlife reservoirs have been established (jackal in Africa, red fox in Europe, raccoon, grey fox and skunk in the U.S.). This disease can be effectively prevented by vaccination, which has been successfully implemented for wildlife using oral baits in the U.S. and Europe. In South Africa, rabies has been documented in domestic dogs and cats, various livestock species, bats, yellow mongoose, black-backed jackal, and bat-eared fox. However rabies is considered a recently introduced infectious disease since it was first established in dogs in KZN in the 1960's. Rabies outbreaks have been increasing in recent years and have occurred all over the country. There is an increased risk of interaction between domestic animals and susceptible wild mammals or humans as competition for resources grows. Rabies is a devastating almost uniformly fatal disease in most mammals. There has also been an increase in wildlife cases in southern Africa. An epizootic of rabies in kudu occurred in Namibia between 1977 and 1983. Rabies is recognized as a significant cause of death in spotted hyenas in the Kalahari. It has also been present in bat-eared fox populations in western South Africa since 1955. Most recently (September 2015), there was an outbreak in the Hoedspruit/Phalaborwa area that caused mortality in impala, jackal, and killed an entire pack of wild dogs (the only local pack outside of Kruger). Rabies can be considered an emerging infectious disease in South Africa. Research is needed with a focus on understanding the disease dynamics in the southern African context. Effective prevention protects domestic animals, humans and wildlife. However, its implementation may be more difficult if there are multiple reservoir hosts. Knowledge gaps exist in the understanding of the epidemiology in wildlife and impact of human activities on disease risks and spread. Different strategies need to be developed for management of rabies in small or isolated versus large complex wildlife populations.

Unlike rabies, tuberculosis is a chronic insidious bacterial disease which affects a wide range of species, including humans. It is widely recognized as an important emerging disease of wildlife globally. However, the impact of chronic disease is often more difficult to determine. Long asymptomatic periods of infection (months to years), variable progression from infection to disease, and the role of complex interactions between environmental, host, and pathogen risk factors contribute to our poor understanding of tuberculosis in most species. South Africa has one of the highest TB human burdens in the world, primarily due to *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Animals, as well as humans can be infected by a number of members of the *M. tuberculosis* complex, including *M. bovis*, *M. tuberculosis*, *M. caprae*, *M. africanum*, *M. pinnipedii*, and others. Tuberculosis has been reported in most mammalian taxa, species of carnivores, small mammals, marine mammals, and others have been reportedly infected. Bovine tuberculosis is typically considered a zoonotic disease that originates in infected cattle, with spillover to human and wildlife hosts. However, there is a paucity of literature describing the epidemiology and disease transmission risks at wildlife-wildlife interfaces, or spillback from wildlife (or humans) to domestic animals. The complexity is amplified in a multi-host ecosystem, where there is the potential for a variety of reservoir species to maintain the disease. There are few countries in the world which have not been affected by TB in wildlife. In South Africa, there has been a steady increase in reported wildlife cases of bovine tuberculosis (2008-2013). Although the first cases of wildlife TB were reported in the 1920's, it has only been more recently (1990's) that the presence of BTB was considered more than an incidental finding in wildlife (buffalo in Kruger). During the past three decades, *M. bovis* has spread throughout South Africa into additional parks and private reserves.

Despite the threat to wildlife populations, there remain large gaps in our understanding of this disease in wild mammals. Extrapolating from cattle, it is believed that *M. bovis* is transmitted through infectious aerosols to close contacts. However, cases in lions and other carnivores suggest that transmission through ingestion of infected prey is a significant risk. The roles of cutaneous exposure (ex. kudu TB) or indirect contact through environmental contamination (e.x. shared grazing; TB in deer and wild boar) indicate that additional information is required to incorporate all modes of transmission into management strategies. Other areas where knowledge is lacking include pathogenesis and development of diagnostic tools for the wide variety of species infected. There is a spectrum of clinical presentations of infection and disease in different species which may lead to misdiagnosis of cases.

Knowledge gaps in our understanding of intra- and interspecies diseases at human-domestic animal-wildlife interfaces require research that will address:

- * Species susceptibility - including the role of host demographic and population density factors
- * Routes of pathogen transmission - and the role of environmental and other factors in altering risks
- * Pathogenesis - host, pathogen, and environmental factors that influence the course of infection and progression to disease
- * Development of tools for detection of pathogen, infection and disease
- * Population level impact of pathogens in different systems
- * Interspecies interactions that affect infectious diseases - including the contribution of human activities

The challenges that we face as we identify research priorities for mammals over the next 2 decades will require:

- * Shift in infectious disease paradigm
 - + Novel pathogens, new hosts, and changing environments
 - + Tools and strategies to assess indirect and long-term impacts on individuals, populations, and ecosystems
- * Implementation of multi-disciplinary approaches
- * Improved access to and availability of animals to study
- * Change in public, political, and regulatory environment
 - + Negotiating social media
 - + Balancing public, political agendas with conservation
 - + Increased regulatory requirements (ex. CITES, DAFF, TOPS, etc.)
- * Funding

We need to embrace a One Health approach to infectious diseases at the human-livestock-wildlife interface as we move into the future. This will require the involvement of human and veterinary infectious disease experts, epidemiologists, disease ecologists, biologists, wildlife managers, diagnosticians, physiologists, environmental scientists, microbiologists, social scientists, politicians, economists, community leaders, farmers, animal rights activists, and members of the public. Strategies must recognize the complexity of interactions and stakeholders.

Future plans should emphasize increased awareness of interface diseases. There is a need to fill basic knowledge gaps to inform strategy and decision-making at all levels. We need to recognize that what we do know may change, and require flexibility in order to address the needs of the next decades of mammal research.

Continuing attempts to do disease ecology research that matters

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SYNOPSIS

I will explore the interactions between science and management of wildlife disease, through a series of case studies in Kruger and Yellowstone National Park. For many of the studies that I have participated in there has been a direct connection to potential management actions, but these are seldom implemented. This is due, in part, to all the other social and economic factors that must also fall into place. Building on Castillo et al. (2006), conservation and management actions require: 1) knowledge about the system, 2) means to conduct an intervention, 3) motivation (either internally or from constituencies) and 4) the legal mandate or social capital required for implementation. In addition, I believe conservation and management actions are more likely when the benefits of the intervention accrue in the short term, and in the same region and agency where costs are incurred. For many of the examples associated with brucellosis around the Yellowstone ecosystem, these costs and benefits are not aligned, leading towards continued wildlife-livestock conflict around disease issues. It seems as though political sensitivity is inversely correlated with the ability to conduct active adaptive management. As a result, the learning process may be slowest on the very issues that are most pressing and important.

The One Health concept is a strategy for expanding interdisciplinary collaborations to improve the health of the environment, animals, and humans. As an umbrella for all sorts of activities, it is widely embraced across many governmental and academic institutions. In a recent analysis of papers on disease dynamics across multiple host species, we found that ecologists and veterinarians still rarely cite one another. Thus, a number of barriers remain despite the calls for increasing collaboration in the fields of One Health. Many fields, departments, and agencies have a role in the One Health approach, and each probably believes their own role to be more important than what others perceive it to be. For example, as a disease ecologist, I tend to think that vaccine development tends to be over-emphasized relative to more ecological manipulations.

Further, the traditional disciplines of One Health (ecology, veterinary and medical sciences) primarily address only one of the facets needed for action—biological knowledge. I believe we need to do a better job integrating social sciences and economics. This is the direction we are pursuing in our Yellowstone research and probably has relevance to One Health research in South Africa. Much of the research emphasis in One Health is focused on the control of infectious disease. I believe the focus should shift from a perspective of controlling disease to promoting health. In some cases this may just be semantics. For example, investigating the factors predisposing some regions or populations to disease outbreaks is both about controlling disease and promoting health. However, promoting health is perhaps more inclusive, allowing for questions about how healthy ecosystems may promote healthy lifestyle choices and vice versa.

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Perspectives on conservation from the boundary of ecology and epidemiology: shielding the flickering lamp of ecological inference

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SYNOPSIS

Any kind of ecology is hard, but infectious disease ecology especially so. The infectious agent is rarely visible, transmission is next to impossible to observe, infection itself may be inapparent, incubation periods variable, infectiousness often brief and frequently highly variable, pathogens may infect multiple and often elusive host species, diagnostic or serological tests are often of low sensitivity and specificity. And on top of this, we may be asked to think about new emerging pathogens, and we may be under pressure to come up with answers fast, and long before we feel we have an adequate understanding on which to evidence them. There are no silver bullets for these problems. But we can strive for the most efficient ways of analyzing data, and most effective ways of generating the most informative datasets.

State-space models (SSMs) have some particular advantages. They allow for the common situation that the process we are really interested in understanding is not directly observable, and recognize that the data we will have is often a biased, indirect reflection of this process. SSMs comprise a process and observation model that enables simultaneous estimation of the parameters governing both how the real process works, and how we are able to observe it. Observation models extend the range of data that may be brought into an analysis. They have a highly flexible structure, which allows multiple observation models to be associated with the same process, thus facilitating the simultaneous integration of a diverse range of data in the identification of one process. They are often developed within a Bayesian framework that facilitates the use of existing understanding, effectively captures the additional value of new data, and appropriately represents and propagates uncertainty.

Any form of perturbation can be viewed as an experiment. It may be that entirely unmanaged 'natural' perturbations give rise to sufficient variation in the dynamics of the process that we can generate some inferential leverage. Alternatively, it may be that pressure to 'manage' a disease situation results in the introduction of an intervention that can - if appropriately monitored - generate information about the process. Indeed, sometimes the only evidence available to inform our management of these processes, is itself generated and shaped by management policy, requiring approaches based on adaptive management. This simultaneous need for intervening and understanding presents us with a difficult conundrum, where real-time management is the only means of generating data, and we must exploit every data point to its full potential with the most powerful means of analysis possible. This requirement for inferential efficiency in understanding infectious disease dynamics demands flexible adaptive approaches to data generation, analysis and management.

Can mathematics be biology's next microscope in disease research at the interface?

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SYNOPSIS

Introduction

Mathematical modelling can be considered as the process of embedding existing knowledge into a mathematical construct. The embedded knowledge is of both qualitative nature, e.g. the law of mass action for the interaction of two species, and quantitative, e.g. the space density of each species at given times. Further, and possibly equally important, one can embed in the model hypotheses in order to test their feasibility and validity. The need for mathematical modelling is motivated by the substantially high complexity of the biological phenomena considered by contemporary biosciences. Indeed, due to technological advances, the possibilities of studying an entire system rather than individual elements or aspects as well as collect measurements of many observable variables at the same time has increased tremendously. Further, solutions to problems of conservation, agriculture, health are sought in the context of bigger a system long term sustainability founded on good understanding of the dynamics of this system. Mathematics provides a suitable medium, where the existing qualitative and quantitative knowledge of the system can be adequately represented as a model. The theoretical analysis and practical simulation may produce results which are beyond the reach of normal observation, experimentation or intuition, thus, giving substance to the statement that Mathematics is Biology's next microscope [3].

Integrating mathematics into biological research. The classical modus operandi of using mathematical/statistical methods in biological research is Research Question - biological observations and/or experiments - collection of data - mathematical/statistical analysis. This modus operandi, quite typical in the past, reflects the limited use of mathematical methods, often only restricted to the analysis of the data, e.g. establishing correlations (N.B. Correlation is not necessarily causality). Such approach seldom results in a practically relevant and useful model. We would like to suggest that efficient and useful application of mathematical modelling it needs to be considered as integral part of all stages of the respective research project. For example, the research question can be considered in the setting of a mathematical model which represents the existing knowledge, identifies gaps, the relative importance of the involved parameters, the dependence of the parameters of interests on the observable variable as well as any pre-existing bifurcation states. The experimental and field work that can be informed by these findings so that when data is collected, hypothesis within the model can be proved or disproved and/or values of parameters of interests reliably identified. The mathematical analysis can also reveal the need for further research leading to a more complete and realistic model, which is also useful in providing answer to the original research question and possibly others that can be generated along the way. A forum for bringing mathematical expertise and/or collaboration at the early stages of a project is essential of the proposed integration of mathematics into biological research and should be an essential part of planned future research infrastructure. There are already some "seeds" of this nature at University of Pretoria. An informal event under the name of "Biomath Coffee" was very useful in facilitating the early involvement of mathematics in biological research. The presentation of student projects still at the stage of formulation of research question was encouraged. The presenters benefitted from the audience's comments and advice and, at least in some cases, fruitful collaboration was established [2], [4], [5].

Output of mathematical models and their analysis. In order to avoid being too general and to be able to provide some specific, we will consider mainly models representing a dynamical system, typically formulated in terms of ordinary and/or partial differential equation.

- * Internal consistency of set of assumption and/or established knowledge represented via the equations of the model.
- * Bifurcation (thresholding) analysis providing the parameter domains of qualitatively different behaviour of the system and characterising this behaviour, e.g. species invading or not, pathogen persisting or getting extinct.
- * Testing the validity of assumptions (hypotheses) by comparing with existing observations of the system
- * Identify the value of parameters of interest by using the values of known parameters and data on the values of observable variables ("microscope" function).
- * Identify knowledge gaps
- * Project scenarios into the future (time-telescope function)
- * Quantify uncertainty (guaranteed range, confidence intervals, sensitivity)

We can give examples from our own work on the evolution of infectious diseases at the interface wild life:life stock:humans, namely, the mathematical models of two infections: *Bartonella* and African Swine Fever Virus (ASFV).

The model of *Bartonella* [2], considers two primary hosts, *Rattus rattus* and *Rattus norvegicus* and two vectors, ticks (Ixodidae family) and fleas (genus *Xenopsylla*). The model takes into account the infection dynamics in each of the four species interlinked via host to vector and vector to host forces of infection. Flow chart is given in Fig.1 (a). The model itself is written

in terms of ordinary differential equations. It provides interesting insights on the infection dynamics and the relative importance of its parameters. In particular, the high sensitivity of the model on the rate of vertical transmission motivated further research (MSc thesis) to accurately estimate its value. The model also reveals a striking need for more detailed biological research on *Bartonella* infections in *Rattus* and their role as carriers. Further, the mathematical analysis proved that the difference in the ectoparasite load of the two *Rattus* species cannot explain alone the difference in their infection prevalence rates.

The main aim of the development of the ASFV model is to investigate a possible natural mechanism for locally occurring extinction [5]. It is motivated by the observed substantially low virus prevalence rate in the tick population in Mkuze Game Reserve. The model focuses on the infection dynamics within a burrow infested with soft ticks (*Ornithodoros porcinus porcinus*). The warthog family inhabiting the burrow is a relatively short prevalence amplification event for the tick population. The flow chart represented in Fig.1 (b) is implemented in terms of system of impulsive differential equation (ordinary and partial). The model reveals that the prevalence in a burrow is maintained via interplay between the mentioned amplification event and the vertical transmission in ticks. Disrupting this mechanism (burrow not inhabited by neonatal warthogs for sufficiently long time) may lead to virus extinction.

Fig. 1. Infection flow charts: S-susceptible, E - exposed, I-infective, R-recovered. (a) *Bartonella* in *R. rattus*, *R. norvegicus*, ticks and fleas (b) ASFV in warthog (host) and ticks (vector) in a burrow, impulsive recruitment = warthog family moving in

Challenges to Mathematics

Despite mathematics' abstract nature, the mathematics development is driven by the needs of human practice. Physics for a long time has been the main inspiration behind many mathematical theories. In contemporary research, Biology is more and more assuming its place [3] and poses new challenges for mathematics. Here we will list two particularly relevant to dynamical systems.

Analysis of nonlinear dynamical systems. Biological systems are highly nonlinear. Despite all of the achievements, the theories of Analysis and the Analysis of Differential Equations are large linear theories. Examples that can be included: (i) Linear diffusion vs Nonlinear diffusion (ii) Nonlinear death rate and extinction in finite time.

Dealing with uncertainty. Parameters of models of biological systems are typically only known to be within particular range rather than to have a precise value. Mathematical theories dealing with set-valued data need further development. One approach is via Interval Analysis. [6]

Constructing mathematical models poses also challenges for biology

Quantitative analysis of species interactions. Constructing mathematical models is build on knowledge regarding functional relationships between species and or factors, e.g. the number of new infections is proportional to the number of existing infectives. Such knowledge is seldom available even on topics which have been well researched. If Biology in general and disease studies in particular, are serious about mathematical modelling future research needs to take qualitative analysis of functional links into consideration.

Relative completeness of knowledge. A mathematical model is a complete construct in the sense that if functions autonomously with prescribed data and parameters. Therefore a model can be useful only if is based on adequate knowledge of all main contributing factors to the studied phenomenon. When constructing a model we necessarily make simplifying assumptions. We take into account some factors, e.g. the life cycle of a disease vector and disregard others, e.g. the phase of the Moon when a vector bites the host mammal, based on their (possibly perceived) impact. The model needs knowledge on all relevant aspects of all factors considered of to be of importance, e.g. age structure of the vector population.

Integrated approach to disease studies at the interface

The processes on the interface of interaction between humans and agriculture on the one side and the wildlife on the other result from processes inherent for each of these to worlds as well as global factors like climate. There significant amount of knowledge on all these three components. Integrating this knowledge can potentially provide better insight into disease dynamics and opportunities for control. The usefulness of some links have been recognised, e.g. the migratory pattern of buffalo herds and the risk of Foot and Mouth disease for cattle, or earth satellite images used in identifying vegetation and matching it to distribution of dung beetles and herbivores. The opportunities for such integrated approach have increased with the availability of computer technology for storing vast amounts of data as well as algorithms to search and link data from different sources and in different formats - the so called Big Data Science. In this setting an integrated approach has to the potential to be an important factor driving future research at the MRI. The immersing at University of Pretoria new Institute for Big Data is possibly a good partner for the MRI in following this approach. Such integration facilitates mathematical modelling since a mathematical model embeds relevant knowledge from all disciplines and spheres of research.

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Wildlife conservation and Veterinary Science - Two sides of the same coin

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SYNOPSIS

Although not as easy to define nowadays as one might think, wildlife is under severe threat with its global population reduced by more than half over the last 45 years. Thus wildlife conservation plays an increasingly crucial role in our efforts to conserve natural ecosystems and consequently global health. However, with the ongoing rapid exploitation of wildlife, often associated with a subsequent transformation of its inhabiting space, and its interlinked social, political, and economic challenges, these efforts become a more and more complex interdisciplinary exercise, requiring input from a wide range of disciplines including the classical biological and veterinary sciences, but also social science, ethics, and law. Prominent recurring research fields linked to wildlife conservation include basic biology, species and population management, inter-species transmission of infectious agents, anthropogenic disturbance, and conservation ethics, to name a few; again underlying the complexity of the overarching task.

Despite some remarkable contributions in the present and the past, it is actually surprising that wildlife conservation is not naturally seen as a domain in the profile of veterinary science. In my presentation I will therefore address this paradox by outlining the eminent position of veterinarians to address many of the key issues related to wildlife conservation, e.g. infectious diseases or reproductive management, thereby strongly advocating for an interdisciplinary and collaborative approach to address the evolving wicked problems related to wildlife conservation.

Presentation milestones

- * Defining wildlife
- * Outlining the interdisciplinary nature of wildlife conservation (WC)
- * Indicating recurring research fields for WC and its evolution in the future context
- * Emphasising the role of veterinary science for WC
- * Advocating for an interdisciplinary and collaborative approach for problem solving

Vision

My envisioned approach would be to create a vibrant cross-disciplinary network of local and global excellence; with experts focussing on key aspects of wildlife-oriented research to address the progressing wicked problems challenging local, regional, and global tasks in wildlife conservation.

The role and contribution of zoos in supporting future advances in wildlife research

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SYNOPSIS

The conduct of basic/applied research is a fundamental requirement for any zoo that desires recognition globally as a quality institution. This is reflected in the accreditation systems of the world's leading zoo and aquarium regional associations. The World Association of Zoos and Aquaria has the expectation that zoos/aquaria become an integral part of the research community as significant contributors of both scientific knowledge and conservation practice. The research conducted in zoos and aquaria globally encapsulates both zoo-based applied science aimed at improving zoo practice (husbandry, welfare etc.), to field-based research that integrates conservation practice with research data collection. The former seeks to establish a scientific basis for zoo best practice and to move away from ideology and emotion. The latter on the other hand, is spearheading a drive to advance the scientific knowledge base from which sound and impactful wildlife conservation practice can emerge. Considering that the flagship species in zoos/aquaria, both aquatic and terrestrial, are largely drawn from Mammalian taxa, it stands to reason that the most research-capable zoos/aquaria can be expected to be at the forefront of the conduct of field-leading research to advance the scientific understanding of these species/taxa with a view to ensuring the sustainability of the respective populations both in their care and in the wild.

Zoos have the potential to support current and future advances in wildlife research through several dimensions, namely (i) the research and technology platforms that larger and better resourced zoos have built over time, often in conjunction with universities; the highly controlled nature of zoological facilities and operations and the interactions with animals; banks of biological material and animal data cutting across thousands of species and hundreds of taxa which can be mined for meaning; specialist animal care staff such as veterinarians, animal health technicians / nurses and husbandry staff are a unique resource many universities and research institutes do not possess; the ability of zoos to bridge the in-situ and ex-situ interface, in which the small animal population management knowledge built up in the zoo situation can be refined and extrapolated to make meaning of in-the-field contexts.

Larger and more resourced zoos globally have built up impressive research infrastructure that serves as research/ technology platforms as well as human capacity development hubs. This currently provides, and will do so even more into the next few decades, a training platform that enables integration of theory and practice because of the animal facilities that zoos / aquaria provide. For example the ability to observe an animal's reproductive and other behavior in a mimicked natural environment while having the ability to sample its reproductive hormones can best be provided in a zoo environment. This is likely to lead to the accelerated development of field portable, rapid biological testing technology for the monitoring of priority species in the field.

The combination of a highly controlled environment that is provided by zoos/aquaria with high-end veterinary expertise offers researchers the capacity to work with large animal species that would otherwise be impossible in a laboratory or field situation. For example, the development of photogrammetric analysis of large mammals could only be best supported by the platform offered by a zoo situation. In the near future it will be eminently possible to develop smart cameras that have remote capacity to undertake detailed analysis of the animal's condition eg. with infra-red sensing of temperature, and interfacing with nano-size analyzers infiltrated into the food of the animal, to get a comprehensive set of analytical data points about the health condition and status of the animal.

Many zoos have extensive biobanks, including cryo-banks, containing biomaterials of critically endangered and sometimes extinct species. With advances in both molecular/cellular resuscitation and reconstruction, the biobanks in zoos, and in some aquaria, have unlimited possibilities to support cutting edge research applications derived from such databanks and enabled by the evolution of technologies and social ethics (eg. for and towards cloning, artificial insemination across similar species etc.)

Future advances in data mining, and advanced computational analysis combined with the right expertise, will enable the extraction of meaning from hundreds of thousands of data points and sets, such as the clinical databases of the National Zoological Gardens of South Africa (NZG), which has over 120 000 entries. To illustrate the potential thereof, every other year six final year veterinary science students from Austria visit the NZG for a month to conduct data mining of the NZG veterinary clinical database and produce between 4 and 6 peer reviewed publications and conference presentations.

Herding for Health: An integrated, community-driven approach to wildlife-livestock compatibility that is both pro-poor and pro-conservation

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ABSTRACT

Landscapes where pastoralist communities and wildlife interact are arguably one of the most important settings where the fate of many livelihoods and wildlife populations will be determined in years to come. This wildlife-livestock interface in Africa represents multiple risks to all present: the spread and control of transboundary animal diseases, including important zoonotic pathogens; various forms of human-wildlife conflict, such as predation; competition for natural resources, like grazing and water; and silo-structured governance systems that need to interact at multiple levels. Recently, the World Organization for Animal Health (OIE) published a standard (Article 8.6.25) in its Terrestrial Animal Health Code that makes allowance for the international trade in beef produced in foot-and-mouth disease (FMD) infected areas should certain conditions be met. In southern Africa zones not free from FMD are closely associated with large conservation areas where African buffalo *Syncerus caffer*, the endemic host of the SAT- viruses of FMD, occur. The new trade standard allows for a commodity-based trade approach which we argue could be used as a catalyst to align efforts at multiple levels by multiple stakeholders to address wildlife-livestock compatibility in an integrated, holistic way. The Herding for Health approach empowers communities through traditional risk mitigation strategies, such as strategic herding and kraaling, in order to manage multiple risks conservationists, state veterinary services, and communities face at the wildlife-livestock interface. Professional herdsmen are trained in a unique suite of skills, such as primary animal health care, holistic planned grazing, record keeping, wildlife avoidance as well as low stress herding techniques. Collective action at the village level enables the smallest to the largest farmer to effectively address risks whilst they comply with beef trade standards and biodiversity conservation agreements. This community-driven approach unlocks incentives for conservation- community-government involvement at the wildlife-livestock interface that are both pro-poor and pro-conservation.

Fig. 1. The daily interaction of wildlife, livestock, and people on the eastern floodplains of the Zambezi Region, Namibia

Fig. 2. A herder tending to his household's valuable stock near Gonarezhou National Park, Zimbabwe

Urban wildlife: reservoirs of infection or sentinels of anthropogenic environmental influence?

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ABSTRACT

Bathyergid rodent moles are subterranean ecosystem engineers, exposed to a wide range of soil-dwelling microbes. With the recent surges in emergent bacterial pathogens infecting humans worldwide, the hunt for potential wildlife reservoirs has intensified. In pristine environments, microbe-bathyergid associations are ancient, whereas in human transformed areas these newly-established microbe-bathyergid interactions are likely to reflect as high-level infections in these naïve vertebrates. The *Bacillus cereus* complex, a ubiquitous assemblage of bacteria, varying in both medical and economic importance, represents a good candidate for assessing bathyergid sentinel potential. Lung samples from 234 individuals (86 *B. suillus* sampled in an urban setting and 45 *C. h. hottentotus*, 53 *G. capensis* and 50 *F. damarensis*, all sampled from natural settings) were screened for *Bacillus* prevalence using PCR assays specific to four gene regions (16S rRNA, groEL, yeaC and gyrB). Nucleotide sequencing and phylogenetic analyses confirmed *B. cereus* complex strain presence in 42 bathyergid lung samples. *Bacillus* prevalence varied by host species and was 45.35% for *B. suillus*, 4.44% for *C. h. hottentotus*, 0% for *G. capensis* and 2% for *F. damarensis*. Differences in *Bacillus* strain prevalence were significant between the four host species evaluated ($\chi^2 = 69.643$; $df = 3$; $p < 0.05$) and between urban and natural sampling localities ($\chi^2 = 70.245$; $df = 3$; $p < 0.05$). Belowground biodiversity is severely understudied and the implications of interactions between different classes of soil biota, such as microbe-bathyergid interactions, on human health are generally overlooked. With continual anthropogenic pollution of once natural environments worldwide, the risk of opportunistic pathogens being introduced into transformed ecosystems has amplified, particularly in developing countries such as South Africa. Consequently, the results of this study which confirmed *Bacillus* genome presence in 45.35% of the bathyergids sampled from an urban environment, highlights the sentinel potential of these soil-dwelling mammals.

Out of Africa: Insights into the illegal pangolin trade and potential health implications

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ABSTRACT

Pangolins (Pholidota: Manidae) are the only group of mammals that have a covering of scales rather than fur, as is more typical for mammals. These secretive, predominantly nocturnal mammals occur at low population densities, are rarely seen, and even more rarely studied. Yet pangolins are extensively used in both Traditional

Fig. 1. Two of Africa's four pangolin species. (a) White-bellied Pangolin (*Phataginus tricuspis*) and (b) Temminck's Ground Pangolin (*Smutsia temminckii*).

African and Traditional Chinese Medicine, and with the collapse of the Asian pangolin populations traders are increasingly looking towards Africa to supply the insatiable demand. An overlooked aspect of this trade is the potential for the transmission of zoonotic agents during the capture, butchering and transport of animals and the risk of disease range expansion associated with these illegal activities. In addition, no studies been conducted to date to determine which disease agents are hosted by southern African pangolins. As a first step in addressing this we have used a combination of broad-range and genus-specific molecular detection approaches to obtain baseline estimates of bacterial prevalence and diversity. These disease data when complemented with estimates of the actual levels of illicit trade that are being collated through a variety of sources, will provide the first estimations of risk. Our preliminary results suggest that the current levels of trade are substantial, and most probably exceed the annual recruitment rates for the species involved. We also found high levels of bacterial infections in pangolins, including numerous instances of apparent co-infection, and at least some of the tentatively identified bacteria have known zoonotic potential. Our results suggest that the illicit trade goes beyond affecting the species being traded and may potentially have broader health implications.

Host-parasite networks in South African small mammals

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ABSTRACT

High host species diversity is thought to have the potential to reduce the prevalence of pathogen vectors such as ticks and fleas in a host community. Such dilution effects have been shown in several small mammal communities in the northern hemisphere but are rarely addressed in the Afrotropical region. Similarly, the number of systematics studies of host-sharing among parasite species is limited. In the current study we aimed to fill this gap in our knowledge by sampling a small mammal community in Ezemvelo/Telperion Nature Reserve, Gauteng Province, South Africa. Over the course of one year a total of eleven small mammal species (nine rodents, two insectivores) was captured during 9216 trap nights in sixteen study plots comprising 391 host individuals. From these a total of 23,088 ticks from 14 species and 1,558 fleas from four species were collected. Several of these are recognised as important vectors of human and livestock pathogens including *Rickettsia conorii*, *Yersinia pestis*, *Theileria parva*, *Anaplasma marginale*, *Babesia bigema* and *Ehrlichia bovi*. The ticks connected between two and eleven host species in an interaction network while the range was smaller for fleas with four to five host species. Habitat type affected the distribution of host species with four being restricted to grassland, two to rocky outcrops and the remaining five species occurring in both habitat types. The latter showed markedly reduced densities on grassland, however, their parasite burdens did not vary with habitat type and the interaction network patterns corresponded to those of the entire community. These results show a high host and ectoparasite diversity and suggest low host specificity for the majority of ectoparasites encountered. Furthermore, the data indicate that host encounter reduction mechanisms may act in habitats with higher small mammal host diversity reducing not the relative but the absolute vector abundance.

The value of genetics in conservation

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ABSTRACT

In conservation-related studies, genetic markers have been used to for a variety of purposes, including to: 1) infer levels of inbreeding in endangered or captive populations; 2) predict connectivity between fragmented populations; 3) estimate current and historical effective population sizes; 4) assess whether loss of genetic variation at adaptively important genes has been compromised by reduction in population size or habitat fragmentation; 5) determine the source of migrants between populations or compare current and historical gene pools; 6) test whether there are dispersal differences between males and females or age classes; and 6) design captive breeding or re-introduction programmes. Using our previous work on African Wild Dogs (lead by Clare Marsden) [1-4] as an example, I will discuss the value of new and old technologies to address these types of questions.

Fig. 1 African wild dog, *Lycaon pictus* [2]

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Conservation Genetics and Management of African Cape Buffalo

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ABSTRACT

The African Cape buffalo (*Syncerus caffer caffer*) is an important herbivore in the savannah ecosystem. As one of the Big Five, this species draws many tourists and trophy hunters to southern Africa. However, bovine tuberculosis, brucellosis, Corridor disease and foot-and-mouth disease all threaten buffalo populations. Consequently, the South African National Parks Board conducted “disease-free” breeding programmes of Kruger National Park (KNP) buffalo to establish populations free of these diseases, while maintaining the high genetic diversity of KNP buffalo [1]. Cape buffalo is also the most valuable species in the wildlife ranching industry, where buffalo are bred, to varying degrees of intensity, to (predominantly) obtain larger horns in successive generations. These privately owned buffalo herds were mainly stocked from “disease-free” populations, such as buffalo from the Addo Elephant National Park (AENP) and those from KNP “disease-free” breeding programmes. However, limited or no studies have been done to investigate the effect that the “disease-free” breeding programmes, and the intensive breeding strategies on private reserves, has had on the genetic structure and diversity of southern African buffalo populations. Using microsatellite markers, we show that the genetic signatures of AENP and KNP buffalo are clearly identifiable in the majority of the private populations. Furthermore, two buffalo populations established from the “disease-free” breeding programme, and 12 privately owned populations still have high genetic diversity. Comparatively, the relict population of AENP showed significantly lower genetic diversity. Therefore, we recommend that “disease-free” buffalo originating from KNP be used to augment the genetic diversity of the AENP population. The “disease-free” breeding programmes, and current breeding strategies of wildlife ranches in this study, maintained and continue to maintain high genetic diversity of buffalo populations in southern Africa. Maintaining high genetic diversity provides populations with greater adaptive potential to survive environmental stressors such as disease outbreaks and climate change [2].

[1] L. Laubscher and L. Hoffman, “An overview of disease-free buffalo breeding projects with reference to the different systems used in South Africa,” *Sustainability*, 4, 3124-3140 (2012).

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A decade of collaborative multidisciplinary research approaches to save species

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ABSTRACT

The NZG as a National Research Facility has a unique position to generate new knowledge, develop core technologies and data pools/collections commensurate with international standards. It has a critical mass of equipment, skills and users and the potential for networking and attracting collaborations. The facility offers unique opportunities for the advancement of science and an interface between science and the public. In particular our strength is bringing together researchers from a variety of disciplines in synergy and an interdisciplinary approach rarely encountered in other research institutions or departments. This approach has over the last decade, and through important partners such as the MRI, broadened our ideas, innovation and formulation of research projects. Together with the MRI, the NZG Biobank is supported as a single port of entry for African wildlife biomaterials for research, biodiversity conservation and biotechnology development purposes. To this end the value of multidisciplinary approaches is evident in several collaborative projects. What comes to mind are collaborative projects on establishing authenticated cell lines from wildlife tissue for the biobank; interrogating the capacity of the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal (HPG) axis function in relation to TB infection in the African lion (*Panthera leo*); a life-table comparison between captive and free-living populations of black and white rhinos; monitoring of growth, recruitment and elephant damage of Marula trees in the Kruger National Park; three-dimensional photogrammetric mass estimation of terrestrial mammals; identifying suitable enzyme immunoassays for monitoring adrenocortical activity based on faecal glucocorticoid metabolite analysis in plains zebra (*Equus quagga*) using an adrenocorticotrophic hormone challenge and the mycobactericidal properties of whole blood and plasma from South African carnivores. Did we in the end collaboratively save any species? We believe that this collaboration has made an impact on species conservation as well as training of the next generation of conservationists, endocrinologists and reproductive biologists.

Effective conservation requires a sound taxonomy: Lessons from recent advances in phylogenetics and phylogeography of Africa's endemic golden moles (family Chrysochloridae)

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ABSTRACT

Golden moles belong to Afrotheria, an ancient clade of placental mammals that ranks among Africa's most enigmatic and endangered, but poorly studied endemic mammals. The group comprises two subfamilies, nine genera and 21 species of which ten species are threatened by anthropogenic destruction and fragmentation of their naturally restricted sandy soil habitat according to latest IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2015. Conservation efforts are jeopardized by uncertain taxon delineations and unresolved phylogenetic relationships based on morphology, cytogenetics and limited molecular data. A sound taxonomy forms an essential baseline for conservation planning and within this context we present a fully-resolved phylogeny for golden moles based on concatenated molecular, morphological and cytogenetic characters. The inferred evolutionary relationships are discordant with current taxonomic subdivisions and uncovered genetically distinct lineages within two genera and cryptic lineages within three species, which form the basis of revised Chrysochloridae classification presented. As the phylogeny offers unique insights into the diversification of an old but range-restricted clade across the African continent, we used molecular dating to place the evolutionary radiation of chrysochlorids in the context of Africa's palaeoclimatic and geological history. Conservation implications of the phylogeny and intra-specific relationships, phylogeography and gene flow (regional/localized) based on additional mitochondrial and nuclear DNA analyses are discussed. The widespread *Amblysomus hottentotus* seems to represent a species complex with several genetically divergent lineages, some of which may be threatened. The endangered *Neamblysomus julianae*, known from three range-restricted, geographically isolated South-African populations. The Kruger National Park population (western limit) is genetically divergent from Tshwane and Modimolle populations (eastern limit) and possible a distinct species. New molecular frameworks will contribute substantially to informed conservation planning for both species and should aim to conserve the integrity of each genetically unique population. Rigorous geographic sampling to delineate taxonomic boundaries of cryptic lineages is ongoing, and emphasizes the importance of a sound taxonomy for effective conservation planning for all threatened chrysochlorids, and species in general.

Fig. 1. An adult Juliana's golden mole.
Credit: Craig Jackson

Fig. 2. A foraging tunnel of Juliana's golden mole visible as soil breakage. Credit: Sarita Maree